

Novafert

D2.3 Environmental impact assessment reports for alternative fertilising products

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Executive Summary

The environmental benchmarking of alternative fertilising products and mineral counterparts has been controversial for the last decades. One of the main reasons is the lack of standardised methods for environmental footprint. In the European Union, the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) is an initiative to harmonise the product footprint of the product sector with a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) based method.

In NOVAFERT Deliverable 2.2, the category rules for the sector of alternative fertilising products were proposed and discussed. This category's rules include the discussion of the Functional Unit, the system boundaries, the allocation system and others. The present deliverable aims to validate and test the methodological choices in Deliverable 2.2 proposed and other methodological developments, such as the adaptation of the Circular Footprint Formula (CFF) to compound alternative fertilising products.

For the validation, 15 product value chains from five different European companies were assessed. The assessment included sensitivity analyses for the most critical methodological questions: functional unit (FU), allocation and CFF. Therefore, the present illustrates the influence of these methodological choices in the final decision-making and stakeholders from the value chain with a nutrient recycler and applicant-end-user perspectives. In particular, the application of the developments of the CFF allowed a holistic life-cycle perspective, including the effect of markets in environmental accounting. An economic analysis was performed to complement the overview of the alternative fertilising products assessed. Then, a second study based on the fertilisation stage for 6 different farming systems in 3 different locations was performed.

The results evidenced the variety of processes, thus environmental hotspots and drivers of the product's footprint (E.g. chemicals, electricity and other nutrient sources). The influence of the functional unit is critical, and the use of complementary ones is encouraged. Nonetheless, the study evidence how the decision-making and the trade-offs among impact categories can change based on the fertilisation needs. Therefore, the PEF-wise method should be used carefully in the communications, though low-impact products could rebound in a higher impact in the application, thus the overall. In general, the PEF-wise methodology proposed in NOVAFERT is valuable for fertilising products benchmarking.

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List of Abbreviations

BBF: Bio-based fertiliser
CAPEX: capital expenditure
CFF: Circular Footprint Formula
EC: European Commission
EF: Environmental Footprint
EU: European Union
EPD: Environmental Product Declarations
EPLCA: The EU Platform on LCA
EoL: End-of-life
FU: Functional Unit
GHG: Greenhouse Gases
IPCC: Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
LCA: Life Cycle Assessment
LCI: Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA: Life Cycle Impact Assessment
OEF: Organizational Environmental Footprint
OPEX: operational expenditure
PCR: Product Category Rules
PEF: Product Environmental Footprint
PEFCR: Product Environmental Footprint Category Rules
SOC: Soil Organic Carbon
TS: Technical Secretariat
WP: Work package

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1. Introduction

The use of mineral fertilisers has clearly contributed to the Green Revolution, resulting in economic growth and high yields in agricultural production (Pingali, 2012). Particularly in the mid-20th century, the use of mineral fertiliser helped combat food insecurity and contributed to economic growth (Pingali, 2012). In general, fertilisers, regardless of mineral or biological origin, are composed of those three main macronutrients: nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium (Daramola & Hatzell, 2023a).

Even though the Haber Bosch process was a breakthrough in nitrous-based mineral fertiliser production, and the synthesis of ammonia and nitric acid from air accelerated industrial agricultural production, the environmental impacts are vast (Wang et al., 2021). A major shortcoming of the Haber-Bosch process is that it is highly energy-intensive and is one of the most energy-consuming processes in the USA (Daramola & Hatzell, 2023a). The nitrogen fertiliser market is mainly made up of Russia, China, Qatar, Saudi Arabia and the United States, which accounted for 46% of global nitrogen exports in 2022. As Russia is holding the largest share (16%), the decrease in nitrogen-based fertilisers in 2022 was evident as the Ukraine conflict disrupted the value chain for natural gas (FAO, 2024, Tothova).

Phosphorus fertilisers are mainly derived from phosphate rock, which is a non-renewable resource and estimated to be depleted in 100 years (Illakwahhi et al., 2024). Meanwhile, phosphorus demand is expected to increase, while the quality of the reserves declines, and therefore production becomes more expensive. Moreover, phosphorus processing is an energy-intensive process, with around 39% of the embodied energy in phosphate fertilisers associated with the energy used in their processing (Daramola & Hatzell, 2023b). With current practices of mineral fertiliser products, Europe needs to import phosphorus as it lacks its own reserves, which directly creates a dependency on other countries, which can lead to geopolitical challenges. Currently, Morocco, Russia, China, Saudi Arabia and the USA hold around two-thirds of the world's phosphorus resources (Witek-Krowiak et al., 2022). Global exports of phosphorus fertilisers decreased by 17 % between 2021 and 2022, highlighting the impact of geopolitical tensions, supply chain disruptions and policy changes on the global fertiliser market (FAO, 2024). Although the use of phosphorus in agriculture is being re-evaluated, as farmers in Europe try to minimise over-fertilisation, exploiting new sources and especially developing smart nutrient recovery systems according to circular economy principles, is crucial to sustain global and European food security.

The economic value of fertilisers is high, as the global market was valued at 191.41 billion EUR in 2024 and is projected to reach around 254.77 billion EUR in 2032, expanding at a Compound Annual Growth Rate of 2.9% in this period (Spherical Insights, 2022). Asia, the Pacific, and Africa are the largest consumers of fertilisers, largely due to population numbers and a shift in agricultural practices utilising mineral fertilisers (Precedence Research, 2024). Contrary to these regions, the quantity of mineral fertiliser application in Europe declined by 9% between 2002 and 2022.

As outlined above, the generation of NPK for mineral fertiliser has major geopolitical and environmental impacts. Additionally, the flow of anthropogenic nitrogen and phosphorus (i.e.,

from fertiliser) into the environment is considered among the nine planetary boundaries (Richardson et al., 2023). Shortcomings of mineral fertilisers are manifold, such as their energy-intensive production, their geopolitical implications, and their environmental impacts especially when used in excess (Nash et al., 2017). The excessive use of mineral fertilisers globally could reach levels that disrupt the earth's biogeochemical flows, influencing the transgression of two of nine planetary boundaries thus a considerable environmental impact (Rockström et al., 2009).

Recently, the EU has changed its approach and promotes responsible fertiliser usage and sustainable farming practices, as outlined in its strategy to ensure the availability and affordability of fertilisers while encouraging environmentally responsible use and the adoption of sustainable farming practices (EU Commission, n.d.-a)

These new measures aim to ensure food security while promoting and shifting towards sustainable and eco-friendly alternatives to minimise and reduce the environmental impact. Simultaneously, the number of consumers who are increasingly preferring organic and more eco-friendly products is rising, with increased awareness and rejection of unsustainable practices. These preferences directly and indirectly favour circular and biobased fertilisers. The environmentally conscious tendencies are supported by governmental policies and regulations that provide subsidies and incentives to farmers. Thus, those actions accelerate demand for organic and biobased fertilisers (BBFs) and a transition towards more sustainable production models (Precedence Research, 2024)

Mineral fertilisers are increasingly questioned, and BBFs are gaining attention as promising alternatives that align with circular economy principles by utilising waste as a resource (Roy et al., 2025). Instead of relying on non-renewable inputs, BBFs are derived from organic waste streams, offering the potential to close nutrient loops and reduce the environmental burden associated with conventional fertiliser production. Still, several challenges persist in the practical implementation of BBFs. One bottleneck lies in the lack of environmental impact comparison standards to benchmark mineral and alternative fertilising products.

2. Goal and scope of the deliverable

To address this challenge, a dedicated Product Environmental Footprint Category Rules (PEF-wise PCR) methodology has been developed within NOVAFERT in Deliverable 2.2.-PEF-wise PCR methodology to implement Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for the environmental assessment of alternative fertilising products.

This methodology proposes a series of LCA normative rules according to the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) framework. It provides a proposal for assessing the environmental impacts of alternative fertilising products, developing a PEF Category Rules (PEFCR) wise method that aims to guide the assessment in a more uniform manner. The methodology presents the specifications in the definitions of the main LCA parameters, including system boundaries, functional unit (FU), life cycle inventory (LCI), allocation rules and impact categories.

To evaluate the effect of the product benchmarking of the proposed methodological solutions and other alternatives, the present deliverable has tested the cited method and other innovations in fifteen alternative fertilising products from five European Companies

3. Materials and methods

3.1. Case studies and primary data collection

This study incorporates case studies of alternative fertilising products sourced from five companies across Europe. To identify suitable case studies, we did an open call on LinkedIn and we sent direct emails to companies of the NOVAFERT partners' network (Figure 1).

Figure 1. LinkedIn publication to announce the open call to participate in the testing of the PEFCR-wise.

The case studies were selected according to the availability of the company to share relevant data for doing the LCA and the relevance of the cases to the objective of this study. The selected companies signed a collaboration agreement for data protection. The company and sensitive information were anonymised.

Upon the establishment of the collaboration agreement, we initiated direct communication with the primary contact responsible for the production of the alternative fertilising products to start the exchange of information for the analysis. Following a preliminary screening study to identify life cycle processes with relevant environmental impact, data sharing started.

This process began with an introductory meeting, followed by email exchanges involving questionnaires and basic data inventories. The communication continued with follow-up presentations to share updates and receive feedback, and a final presentation of the results for review, ensuring that confidentiality is maintained.

3.2. Life Cycle Assessment

3.2.1. Functional Unit a System Boundaries

In the present, the alternative fertilising products are considered intermediate products, as they serve as inputs in the production of final goods. Therefore, the declared unit (equal to reference flow) is applied considering 1 kilogram (kg) of fertiliser product.

However, acknowledging that this declared unit is limited for the comparability of fertiliser products, the analysis also includes the functional unit of mass of nutrient: kg Nitrogen (N), kg Phosphorus pentoxide (P₂O₅) and kg Potassium oxide (K₂O).

The analysis includes a *Cradle-to-gate* perspective, which includes the following life cycle stages and processes (Figure 2):

- Raw material acquisition and pre-processing. According to D2.2, if the raw material does not have an economic value at the farm/factory gate, it is regarded as residual or waste, and there is no allocation of an upstream burden.
- Transportation and collection systems of the raw material to the manufacturing place.
- Manufacturing process at the manufacturing plant, including all the process steps.

The distribution until the end user (farm or retail) is excluded to harmonise the data among case studies.

Figure 2. System boundaries and scheme of the life cycle processes from a Cradle to Gate perspective.

3.2.2. Life Cycle Inventory

The Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) integrates the energy and mass balances that interact from the system with the Technosphere and biosphere. These processes are also called foreground. It contains company-specific primary data about:

- The list of fertiliser ingredients, their volumes and their transport to the manufacturing plant.
- The nutritional analysis of the alternative fertilising products
- Energy and water consumption in fertiliser manufacturing operations.

Information from other sources was used to complement missing data such as in the case of direct and indirect emissions from processing, for example for emissions to air from fuel combustion.

3.2.3. Allocation Rules

In the case of multifunctionality in a process or system, meaning that there is more than one product created, and when subdivision of the system is not possible, two allocation rules have been used to assess the impacts, in this order:

- **Economic allocation:** allocating inputs and outputs associated with multi-functional processes to the co-product outputs in proportion to their relative market values.
- **Biophysical allocation:** allocating inputs and outputs associated with multi-functional process or facility in line with a relevant, quantifiable physical relationship between the process inputs and co-product outputs (for example, mass or energy).

In this study, a few systems result in multiple coproducts, requiring the application of either physical or economic allocation methods to appropriately assign environmental impacts. To test the influence of the chosen allocation method on the results, a sensitivity analysis is carried out.

This analysis involves applying different allocation factors and observing the resulting variations in environmental impact distribution to evaluate the reliability and stability of the assessment conclusions.

3.2.4. Software and background database

The software used for Life Cycle modelling is OpenLCA v.2.4 (GreenDelta, 2023) and the database Ecoinvent v.3.10 Cutoff System Model (Ecoinvent, 2023) for the background processes.

3.2.5. Life Cycle Impact assessment methods

The impact assessment method used is based on the Environmental Footprint Method. Version 3.1 (EU Commission JRC, 2022) and includes the impact categories shown in Table 1. These impacts categories are studied in the analysis, with a specific attention to the categories of Acidification, Climate Change and Eutrophication (Zuiderveen et al., 2023)

Table 1. Impact categories included in the Environmental Footprint Method by the JRC.

Impact category	Unit	Abbreviation
Acidification	mol H ⁺ -Eq	AC
Climate change	kg CO ₂ -Eq	CC
Ecotoxicity: freshwater	CTUe	ETfw
Energy resources: non-renewable	MJ, net calorific value	ERnr
Eutrophication: freshwater	kg P-Eq	Eutrfw
Eutrophication: marine	kg N-Eq	Eutrm

Impact category	Unit	Abbreviation
Eutrophication: terrestrial	mol N-Eq	Eutrt
Human toxicity: carcinogenic	CTUh	HTc
Human toxicity: non-carcinogenic	CTUh	HTnc
Ionising radiation: human health	kBq U235-Eq	Irhh
Land use	dimensionless	LU
Material resources: metals/minerals	kg Sb-Eq	Teae
Ozone depletion	kg CFC-11-Eq	OD
Particulate matter formation	disease incidence	Pmf
Photochemical oxidant formation: human health	kg NMVOC-Eq	POFhh
Water use	m ³ world Eq deprived	WU

3.3. Sensitivity Analysis of methodological choices

In line with the objective of the present deliverable, “methodological validation and testing of the PEFCR-wise methodology for alternative fertilising products”, two relevant sensitivity analyses were performed to assess the change in the decision-making related to:

- The functional unit (see section 3.2.1 and 5.5)
- The economic allocation (see section 3.2.3 and 5.6)

3.4. Circular Footprint formula

A non-resolved question in the previous deliverable and developed in the present deliverable is the adaptation of the Circular Footprint Formula (CFF) to the compound alternative fertilisers.

Challenges in the adaptation of CFF to compound alternative fertilisers

There are two challenges: i) the inclusion of alternative compound fertilisers in the assessment and this multifunctionality; and ii) the adaptation of the CFF to the nutrient recycling systems and bio-based fertiliser industry. Therefore, we have first conducted an analytical assessment and tested it in a case study. This is a living research study so it is permeable to other interpretations and further case studies and innovations will be performed.

Adaptation of CFF to compound alternative fertilisers: an analytical approach

Given the generic new CFF formula from Environmental Footprint Method (Eq-1):

$$CFF = (1 - R) \cdot E_v + R_{in} \cdot \left(A_{in} \cdot E_{rec} + (1 - A_{in}) \cdot E_v \cdot \frac{Q_{in}}{Q_p} \right) + (1 - A_{out}) \cdot R_{out} \cdot (E_{rec} - E_v \cdot \frac{Q_{out}}{Q_p}) \quad \text{(Eq-1)}$$

Where R_{in} is the input content recycled material of the inputs; A_{in} is the factor to represent the demand of the inputs; E_{rec} is the impact of the recycling process; E_v is the impact of the virgin material; $\frac{Q_{in}}{Q_p}$ is the quality ratio of the inlet product; R_{out} is the output recycled material and $\frac{Q_{out}}{Q_p}$ is the quality ratio of the output product.

The following equation will be used for the integration of the NPK. However, carbon content is excluded from the present equation, but it could be included in a further assessment, together with other micronutrients mentioned such as Ca, for example.

Firstly, for the first part of the CFF equation here we developed the side of the consumption (Eq-2):

$$I_{cons,NPK} = R_{in} \cdot (A_{in} \cdot E_{rec}) + (1 - A_{in}) \cdot R_{in} \cdot \left(\frac{C_{in,N}}{C_{p,N}} \cdot E_{v,N} \cdot \frac{Q_{in,N}}{Q_{p,N}} + \frac{C_{in,P}}{C_{p,P}} \cdot E_{v,P} \cdot \frac{Q_{in,P}}{Q_{p,P}} + \frac{C_{in,K}}{C_{p,K}} \cdot E_{v,K} \cdot \frac{Q_{in,k}}{Q_{p,k}} \right)$$

(Eq-2)

Where $I_{cons,NPK}$ is the impact of the consumer of the product; $C_{in,i}$ and $C_{p,i}$ are the nutrient content i being the nutrients (N, P and K). Consistency in NPK content units is relevant, i.e. kg of N, P and K; or Kg of N, P₂O₅, and K₂O.

Once the CFF equation for consumption was developed, we developed the side of the nutrient recycler or alternative fertiliser producer (Eq-3):

$$I_{prod,NPK} = (1 - A_{out}) \cdot R_{out} \cdot E_{rec} - (1 - A_{out}) \cdot R_{out} \cdot \left(\frac{C_{out,N}}{C_{p,N}} \cdot E_{v,N} \cdot \frac{Q_{out,N}}{Q_{p,N}} + \frac{C_{out,P}}{C_{p,P}} \cdot E_{v,P} \cdot \frac{Q_{out,P}}{Q_{p,P}} + \frac{C_{out,K}}{C_{p,K}} \cdot E_{v,k} \cdot \frac{Q_{out,k}}{Q_{p,k}} \right)$$

(Eq-3)

Where $I_{prod,NPK}$ is the impact of the nutrient recycler.

The CFF expressed in its completely traditional way (not correct in formal terms) would be:

$$CFF_{N,P,K} = R_{in} \cdot (A_{in} \cdot E_{rec}) + (1 - A_{in}) \cdot R_{in} \cdot \left(\frac{C_{in,N}}{C_{p,N}} \cdot E_{v,N} \cdot \frac{Q_{in,N}}{Q_{p,N}} + \frac{C_{in,P}}{C_{p,P}} \cdot E_{v,P} \cdot \frac{Q_{in,P}}{Q_{p,P}} + \frac{C_{in,K}}{C_{p,K}} \cdot E_{v,k} \cdot \frac{Q_{in,k}}{Q_{p,k}} \right) \\ + (1 - A_{out}) \cdot R_{out} \cdot E_{rec} - (1 - A_{out}) \cdot R_{out} \\ \cdot \left(\frac{C_{out,N}}{C_{p,N}} \cdot E_{v,N} \cdot \frac{Q_{out,N}}{Q_{p,N}} + \frac{C_{out,P}}{C_{p,P}} \cdot E_{v,P} \cdot \frac{Q_{out,P}}{Q_{p,P}} + \frac{C_{out,K}}{C_{p,K}} \cdot E_{v,k} \cdot \frac{Q_{out,k}}{Q_{p,k}} \right)$$

(Eq-4)

The Q_{out}/Q_p ratio should be integrated as 1 by default. There is a wide discussion in the agronomic field about this point but the last conclusion is that the organic/alternative fertilisers do not replace all the NPK needs because at some points of the crop stage fast release nutrients

are needed. In general, 1 unit of N, P or K provided by these products replaces 1 unit of the mineral counterparts.

Selection of mineral nutrient counterparts

One relevant point is the reference product (Ev) for the supply of different nutrients. For the present study, single fertilisers (ammonium nitrate, superphosphate and potassium chloride) were chosen.

Coefficient A and examples

The values of the A coefficient are the main factor for the split of the environmental burdens and credits from the recycling process or recycling technology. According to Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) and Organisation Environmental Footprint (OEF), there are 3 main values (0.2, 0.5, and 0.8) that are normally used depending on the demand and characteristics of the secondary products compared to the primary counterparts (Table 2).

A value would vary among fertilising products and other parameters (temporal availability, price frames). We had identified some of them with similar characteristics to the commercial ones. Therefore, the value that would be applied would be 0.2 due to the high price of selling recovered products compared to the commercial counterparts. Furthermore, the quality ratio that aims to correct quality differences is 1, which means equal functionality.

On the other hand, there are some specific alternative fertilising products whose origin or composition makes them less interesting to the farmers, and they have a low price; therefore, the A values would be higher than 0.8. Both considerations and the use of other values would be a clear option for these products due to the wide range of quality variability found.

Table 2. Definition of coefficient A and values.

Price and demand of secondary products	A value
More high-quality secondary material demanded than produced (e.g. many metals, glass, ...); indicator: market price is close to / same as primary	0.2
The market situation is more balanced or unknown	0.5
The market price is very low compared to primary products	0.8

3.5. Economic analysis

The environmental assessment is complemented with a Life Cycle Cost (LCC) analysis to evaluate the economic profitability and viability of the project. Similar to the environmental LCA, an LCC gathers all data related to costs over the entire life cycle of the product or system, so that stakeholders can identify cost-intensive hotspots, evaluate trade-offs and optimise investment decisions.

When relevant, an LCC also considers potential revenues, which are treated as negative costs, reducing the total net cost of the system. In the context of NOVAFERT, one potential revenue is the avoided costs of processing waste for the companies using it as input. These can be considered financial gains, reducing overall costs.

Despite having 15 different products being produced in different installations across Europe, a harmonised LCC has been carried out based on the economic model guidelines described in Towler & Sinnott (2008) for project costing and plant design.

CAPEX and OPEX calculations

One of the most used tools in LCC is the Capital Expenditures (CAPEX) and Operational Expenditures (OPEX) economic calculation:

- CAPEX represents the one-time cost investment to prepare the pilot for startup. It includes all construction costs, processing and handling equipment, site preparation, and non-process structures. CAPEX can be roughly divided into the sum of the fixed capital investment, which is the total cost of the plant for start-up (including the cost of design, construction, equipment, etc.) and working capital investment, which is the additional operating investment needed when starting up, so the costs for the labour, services and materials required to start the operation of the plant.
- OPEX represents the ongoing expenses incurred during the day-to-day functioning of the project. These costs include salaries, utilities, rent, maintenance, raw materials, and other operational costs. Annual OPEX can be grouped into direct manufacturing costs, fixed manufacturing costs and general expenses.

The data required to evaluate the profitability of the NOVAFERT project has been obtained through a combination of primary and secondary data. For CAPEX, data have been mainly provided by the companies, while OPEX values have been estimated from the inventories developed for the environmental LCA (found in Annexe I). When company-specific data was missing, variable operational costs were sourced from the database Ecoinvent (v.3.10) when available and supplemented with literature as a final resource.

Fixed costs of production (included within both CAPEX and OPEX) are the costs associated with building the plant itself, which will be incurred regardless of the plant's operation rate or output. These costs have been estimated using fixed ratios taken from Towler & Sinnott (2008), as described in Tables 3 and 4.

Labour costs relating to production have been estimated and harmonised using the same unified salary model. This approach ensures that there are no wage disparities between products due to their geographical location.

Table 3. List of Ratios for the Estimation of Fixed Capital Costs. Source: Towler & Sinnott (2008).

Cost	Factor
Equipment installation, including foundations and minor structural work.	0.25
Piping, including insulation and painting.	0.2
Instruments and automatic process control systems.	0.2
Electricity, power, and lighting.	0.15
Process buildings and structures.	0.2
Structures and constructions.	0.1
Site preparation.	0.05
Machinery built from stainless steel.	1
Offsites-OSBL	0.4
Design and engineering	0.2
Contingency	0.1

Table 4. List of Ratios for the Estimation of Fixed Operation Costs. Source: Towler & Sinnott (2008).

Cost	Factor
Supervision	0.05
Maintenance	0.04
Taxes and insurance	0.015
Land rent	0.015
Environmental fees	0.01

Assumptions

- The LCC has considered all economic flows from the early construction stages until the processing of the product. However, the end-of-life stage (plant dismantling or revamping) has been excluded due to data availability and a prioritised focus on the initial investments for production.
- All costs and revenues were quantified in euros (€).
- A lifetime of 25 years for the equipment was assumed when calculating depreciation.

3.6. Assessment of the application stage in the field of alternative fertilising products

The PEF-wise method for BBFs assesses impacts from the sourcing of raw materials through to the delivery of BBFs to the cultivation site (Cradle-to-gate). It did not take into consideration the application and use stage of BBFs. However, this study was a complementary assessment, *cradle-to-grave*, to include the agricultural application stage and examine how this phase may influence decision-making. Therefore, the functional unit was changed to the **fertilisation of 1 hectare per year**. As there were no primary data on application rates for all the assessed fertilisers, and these vary by crop type, soil, and region, the study first estimated application rates per fertiliser. Considering this variability, scenarios were created based on the NPK recommendations for 6 different types of farming (field crops, horticulture, wine, milk, other grazing livestock, granivores and mixed-Table 5. NPK recommendations for EU27 for different types of farming from FADN (2024) (EU Commission, n.d.-b)Table 5) in Europe and optimised by the nutrient profile of each fertiliser. Data from the 2022 Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) for EU27 is used as baseline (EU Commission, n.d.-b). In the sensitivity analysis, country-specific data were incorporated to explore the impact of regional differences on the results. NPK application rates were calculated considering fertiliser recommendations (q/farm) and the arable land (ha/farm).

Table 5. NPK recommendations for EU27 for different types of farming from FADN (2024) (EU Commission, n.d.-b)

Type of Farming	N (kg/ha)	P ₂ O ₅ (kg/ha)	K ₂ O (kg/ha)
Field crops	84.498	24.574	27.559
Horticulture	155.710	90.586	147.840
Milk	105.379	18.703	24.403
Other grazing livestock	57.186	13.463	15.525
Granivores	68.830	13.720	19.188
Mixed	85.114	18.657	23.487

To not exceed the required NPK recommendation per crop, a maximum application rate for each BBF was calculated and complemented with the application of synthetic fertilisers to meet remaining nutrient shortfalls. The following synthetic fertilisers were selected based on their market share (EU Commission, 2024):

- Urea for N (46-0-0), representing 64% of the nitrogenous fertiliser market.
- Superphosphate for P₂O₅ (0-46-0), representing 62% of the phosphatic fertiliser market.
- Potassium chloride for K₂O (0-0-60), representing 62% of the potassic fertilisers market.

Following PEF methodology, emissions associated with fertiliser application were modelled based on the amount of each fertiliser applied. Emissions were differentiated per BBF type and cover:

- NH₃ (air): from N-fertiliser application
- N₂O (air): direct and indirect, from N-fertiliser application

- NO₃ (water): leaching from nitrogen fertilisers
- PO₄ (water): leaching and run-off of soluble phosphate from P-fertiliser application
- P (water): soil particles containing phosphorus from P-fertiliser application

Direct and indirect N₂O emissions caused by nitrogen fertilisation were estimated based on the total nitrogen content of the fertiliser and considering default emissions factors of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2019) (See D2.2 PEF-wise PCR methodology to implement LCA for the environmental assessment of BBFs). The baseline included the calculations for wet climates, but as these factors vary by dry and wet climates, a sensitivity analysis was conducted. P emissions were modelled as the amount of P applied to the agricultural field. CO₂ emissions from inorganic compounds mixed with BBFs were not estimated due to a lack of available data on the analysed fertilisers.

The assessment also included the emissions from transporting the fertiliser to the field and operating the machinery used for fertiliser application. For this assessment, the following assumptions were made:

- A mean transport distance of 50 km from the production site to the field was used to estimate the emissions related to the transport of the required BBF and synthetic fertiliser.
- Fertilising methods were selected from the Ecoinvent dataset as proxies considering the fertiliser form: liquid, pelletized or solid (Table 6).

Table 6. Fertilising method according of each analysed fertiliser

Fertilising method	Fertilisers
Injection	P1, P9, P10, P11, P12, P14, P15
Broadcaster	P6, synthetic fertilisers
Rig	P2, P3, P4, P5, P9, P10, P13

- The impacts of fertilising methods are given per hectare in the Ecoinvent dataset. However, the assessment included the fertilisation with alternative fertilising products and synthetic fertiliser to supplement nutrient deficiencies. Except for P6, alternative and synthetic fertilisers were applied using different fertilising methods. For this reason, the proportion of alternative and synthetic fertilisers was calculated based on the nutrient profile of each option. The share corresponding to N content was used to allocate the environmental impacts associated with the fertilising method of each type of fertiliser.

Sensitivity analysis of the Use on Field of the alternative fertilising products

To validate the methodology for assessing the application phase of alternative fertilising products, the following sensitivity analyses were performed to assess the change in the decision-making related to:

- Regional variability: Country-specific data for Finland and Spain were used instead of the baseline to explore the impact of regional differences on the results, considering Finland as a wet climate and Spain as a dry climate and using the associated emission factors (IPCC, 2019, as cited in Novafert, 2024) to calculate direct and indirect emissions
- Inclusion of the emissions of heavy metals: Due to limited data on the heavy metals content of the analysed fertilisers, these emissions were not included in the environmental assessment. However, for P6 there was available a detailed analysis of its composition and an environmental analysis, including heavy metal content, was performed.

Economic Analysis of the Use on Field of the alternative fertilising products

The environmental assessment was complemented with an economic analysis of the application phase of the fertilisers. Cost data for synthetic fertilisers, transport and fertilising methods were sourced from the database Ecoinvent (v.3.10).

Additionally, as there was no primary data available for the price of the alternative fertilising products, an analysis was performed to determine the cost-competitive price. This approach identifies the break-even price at which alternative fertilising products would be economically competitive compared to the baseline scenario of using exclusively synthetic fertilisers. To calculate this, the variable price of BBF was calculated as the difference between the total fertilisation costs associated with the scenario that uses BBF (including transport and application-related costs and market costs of complementary synthetic fertilisers) and the fertilisation costs from the scenario of using only synthetic fertilisers (including transport, application and market price for synthetic fertilisers).

4. Case studies description

This research includes 13 case studies of fertiliser products, collected from five different companies in Europe. The following section provides a description of each fertiliser, its production process, and the considerations made when constructing its respective Life Cycle Inventory with primary data from the company.

4.1 Company A (P1, P2, P3, P4 and P5)

An overview of the alternative fertilising products produced by Company A, together with their description and the nutrient profile, is shown in the following Table 7.

Table 7. Description of fertilisers (P1-P5) produced by Company A.

Product number	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	
Description	Liquid fertiliser produced from liquid biodegradable waste that is stabilized with quicklime and blended with urea and potassium chloride (KCl).	Solid fertiliser produced from biodegradable waste that is stabilized with quicklime.	Solid fertiliser produced from biodegradable waste that is stabilized with quicklime and blended with compost.	Solid fertiliser produced from biodegradable waste that is stabilized with quicklime and ash.	Solid fertiliser produced from biodegradable waste that is stabilized with quicklime and ash and blended with compost.	
Co-products in the production	None	None	None	None	None	
Nutrient profile	N	15.40%	1.60%	1.10%	1.60%	1.20%
	P₂O₅	4.12%	2.75%	2.75%	4.12%	3.21%
	K₂O	21.68%	0.24%	0.36%	3.61%	1.08%

The production process of each fertiliser is shown and detailed in the following diagrams (Figures 3-7). It includes the transport of the raw materials required for the production of the fertiliser, the electricity and water required for the plant operation and the fuel required for the wheel loader that stabilises the biodegradable waste with quicklime. The transport to the end user was excluded from the scope of the analysis.

Figure 3. Product 1 Process diagram.

Figure 4. Product 2 Process diagram.

Figure 5. Product 3 Process diagram.

Figure 6. Product 4 Process diagram.

Figure 7. Product 5 Process diagram.

LCI and Data Quality Considerations

The LCI for fertilisers P1, P2, P3, P4 and P5 is detailed in Annexe I. The construction of these LCIs used primary data shared by the companies and involved the following considerations:

- Electricity and water consumption for Plant Operation were included, considering the annual consumption and the total treated biodegradable waste.
- CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O emissions from diesel combustion from the machinery used in the process were estimated (IPCC, 2006, Chapter 2).
- Volatized NH₃ and N₂O emissions related to lime application were estimated considering the amount of applied lime (IPCC, 2006, Chapter 11).

4.2 Company B (P6)

An overview of the alternative fertilising products produced by Company B, together with their description and the nutrient profile, is shown in **Error! No s'ha trobat l'origen de la referència.**

Table 8. Description of fertiliser (P6) produced by Company B.

Product number		P6
Description		Pelletized solid fertiliser produced from the digestion of pig slurry.
Co-products in the production		Electricity Production
Nutrient profile	N	12.76%
	P₂O₅	10.31%
	K₂O	6.51%

The production process of P6 is shown and detailed in the following diagram (Figure 8). The P6 production process is based on the integrated valorisation of pig slurry, producing both fertiliser P6 and electricity.

The process starts with anaerobic digestion of the slurry, resulting in the production of biogas and digestate. The biogas is subsequently blended with natural gas and utilised in a combined heat and power unit, supplying thermal and electrical energy to the facility and the external grid.

The digested pig slurry is then separated into a solid fraction and a liquid fraction. The liquid fraction is acidified with sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄), degassed, and evaporated. The resulting concentrate from the evaporation and the solid fraction are dried and pelletized to form the final P6 fertiliser product.

Figure 8. Product 6 Process diagram.

LCI and Data Quality Considerations

Live Cycle Inventory for fertilisers P6 is detailed in Annexe I. The construction of this LCI used primary data shared by the company and includes the following considerations:

- Electricity and water consumption related to plant operations were accounted for.
- Biogenic CO₂ and CH₄ emissions resulting from the anaerobic digestion of pig slurry were estimated based on the chemical composition of the produced biogas.
- CO₂ emissions from the combustion of natural gas were estimated based on natural gas consumption and its emission factor (Practical Guide for Calculating Greenhouse Gas Emission, 2019.).
- NO_x, SO₂, and formaldehyde emissions were estimated using a company analysis by TÜV Rheinland, based on the composition of fuels used: 97% natural gas and 2.7% biogas.

Additionally, to assess the environmental impact of P6 production, an economic allocation method has been applied. Since P6 is a co-product of the pig slurry processing operation (along with electricity), the allocation is based on each product's share of the total annual revenue. Primary data from the company is used to estimate the revenue for selling electricity to the grid. As there is no available data on the price of the P6, it is considered the common price of compost for industrial processes. This price is tested through sensitivity analysis to evaluate its influence on the overall results.

The environmental impact and economic costs attributed to P6 are therefore allocated based on its 0.61% contribution to the total annual revenue (Table 9).

Table 9. Economic allocation method applied for P6.

Co-products	Price	Unit	Annual Production	Unit	Annual Revenue (Unit	% of Total Annual Revenue
Electricity	0.17 €	€/kWh	98019485	kWh/year	16,640,522.92	€/year	99.39%
P6	35 €	€/t P6	2962	t/year	288,600.52	€/year	0.61%

4.3 Company C (P7, P8, P9 & P10)

An overview of the alternative fertilising products produced by Company C, together with their descriptions and the nutrient profile, is shown in Table 10.

Table 10. Description of fertilisers (P7, P8, P9 & P10) produced by Company C.

Product number		P7	P8	P9	P10
Description		Solid fertiliser produced from mixed sludge, primary sludge and peat, which are stabilised with slacked lime, which is manufactured from hydrated burnt lime.	Solid fertiliser produced from mixed sludge.	Liquid fertiliser is produced from concentrated potato cell sap, a by-product of potato starch processing.	Liquid fertiliser produced from vinasse, concentrated from the residual growth medium of yeast production.
Co-products in the production		None	None	None	None
Nutrient profile	N	0.65%	0.33%	1%	3.3%
	P ₂ O ₅	0.29%	0.14%	1.05%	0%
	K ₂ O	0.03%	0.01%	3.61%	9.4%

The production process of each fertiliser is shown and detailed in the following diagrams (Figures 9-12).

For P7 (Figure 9), it includes the transport of the raw materials required for the production of the fertiliser. The process of hydration of the burnt lime, which takes place in a different plant, was included, considering the added water and the fuel for the machinery that mixes it with the burnt lime. In the plant operation, the fuel required for the machinery for mixing and sieving was included.

For P8 (Figure 10), it includes the transport of the mixed sludge and the fuel required for mixing and sieving it.

For P9 and P10 (Figure 11-12) it only includes the transport to the intermediate storage as no additional manufacturing process from the main raw material is required.

The transport to the end user was excluded from the scope of the analysis.

Figure 9. Product 7 Process diagram.

Figure 10. Product 8 Process diagram.

Figure 11 Product 9 Process diagram

Figure 12 Product 10 Process diagram

LCI and Data Quality Considerations

- CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O emissions from light fuel oil combustion are estimated for P7 and P8 (IPCC, 2006, Chapter 2).
- Volatized NH₃ and N₂O emissions related to lime application are estimated considering the amount of applied lime for P7 and P8 (IPCC, 2006, Chapter 11).

In products 9 and 10, the fertilisers are produced using raw materials that are byproducts of potato starch and yeast production. These byproducts were not considered as waste, as they have an economic value in the market and, thus, an economic allocation of the associated environmental impacts was performed (Table 11).

The price for the byproducts was based on primary data shared by the company, and the price for the products from which the byproduct is generated is sourced from the Ecoinvent database. In the case of yeast production, fodder yeast was used as a proxy.

Since the raw materials are concentrated from these byproducts, but there was no primary data on the concentration processes, the concentration rate was estimated by comparing the NPK content of the byproducts with the NPK of the final fertiliser. For concentrated potato cell sap, it was considered that 5t of potato cell sap was produced as a byproduct from processing 1t of potato starch, with a concentration rate of 3.33% (Li & Zhang, 2010). For concentrated vinasse from yeast production, it was considered that 2.33t of vinasse results from producing 1t of yeast (Lisičar-Vukušić et al., 2019), with a concentration rate of 5.15% (Gómez & Correa, 2024). A sensitivity analysis was carried out to assess how variations in the estimated concentration rates affect the overall results.

Table 11. Economic Allocation for P9 and P10

Product	Raw material	Economic Allocation of the impact
P9	Main product: Potato starch	94.33%
	By-product: Concentrated potato cell sap	5.67%
P10	Main product: Fooder yeast	99.67%
	By-product: Concentrated vinasse	0.33%

4.4 Company D (P11 and P12)

An overview of the alternative fertilising products produced by Company D, together with their descriptions and the nutrient profile, is shown in Table 12.

Table 12. Description of fertilisers (P11-P12) produced by Company D.

Product number		P11	P12
Description		Pelletized Solid fertiliser produced from cow manure and mixed with biochar from apple cultivation residues.	Pelletized Solid fertiliser produced from cow manure and mixed with biochar from vineyard residues.
Co-products in the production		None	None
Nutrient profile	N	4.76%	3.58%
	P ₂ O ₅	0.98%	0.80%
	K ₂ O	1.14%	1.06%

The production process of each fertiliser is shown and detailed in the following diagram (Figure 13). P11 and P12 production starts with a pre-treatment of the cow manure at the farm level, where sawdust is added. The pre-treated material is then transported to the manufacturing plant and combined with the bark structuring agent. The mixture goes through aerobic composting, sieving, and thermal drying. The final compost is mixed with biochar (from apple cultivation residues for P11 and vineyard residues for P12) and pelletized to produce the final P11 fertiliser product.

Figure 13. Product 11 and Product 12 Process diagram.

LCI and Data Quality Considerations

- CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O emissions from diesel combustion are estimated (IPCC, 2006, Chapter 2).
- Direct N₂O and indirect NH₃ are estimated (IPCC, 2006, Chapter 10).

4.5 Company E (P13, P14 and P15)

An overview of the alternative fertilising products produced by Company E, together with its description and nutrient profile, is shown in Table 13.

Table 13. Description of fertilisers (P13, P14 and P15) produced by Company E.

Product number		P13	P14	P15
Description		Liquid Fertiliser produced from digestate	Ammonium Sulphate Liquid Fertiliser produced from digestate	Solid Fertiliser produced from digestate
Co-products in the production		None	None	None
Nutrient profile	N	2.96%	26.19%	93.38%
	P ₂ O ₅	0.15%	0.00%	22.21%
	K ₂ O	97.14%	0.00%	16.79%

The production process of each fertiliser is shown and detailed in the following diagrams (Figures 14 and 15). P13, P14 and P15 production comes from a multi-process system that starts with the solid and liquid separation of a digestate using the polymer polyacrylamide and machinery that operates with electricity, which results in a solid and liquid fraction.

The liquid fraction is processed with flotation, ultrafiltration and reverse osmosis. The rejection streams from these filtration units are partly discarded and partly mixed with sulfuric acid processed through an evaporation unit to concentrate the nutrient content. This processing produces two fertilisers: P13 and P14

The solid fraction is dried in a bio-drying unit and generating a solid rejection. The dried solid fraction is then pelletized using electricity to produce the final P15 product.

Figure 14. Product 13 and Product 14 Process diagram.

Figure 15. Product 15 Process diagram.

LCI and Data Quality Considerations

- The digestate is treated as a waste material, and the environmental burdens from the upstream waste treatment processes that generated the digestate are not included in the assessment.
- NH₃ emissions from bio-drying are estimated (IPPC 2019, Chapter 10)

To evaluate the environmental impacts of the three produced fertilisers, two allocation methods are used. First, a physical allocation approach is implemented for the solid-liquid separation process. Thus, the consumption of polymer and electricity was allocated proportionally to the mass of the resulting solid and liquid fractions.

Second, since the processing of the liquid fraction generates two different fertilisers in different quantities, an economic allocation of the associated impacts was performed for this step. The price of P13 was estimated based on typical market values for compost used in industrial processes. The price of P14, which was considered comparable to ammonium sulphate, was taken from the Ecoinvent database. A sensitivity analysis was carried out to assess how variations in the assumed prices for P13 and P14 influence the overall results. The environmental impact and economic costs attributed to P13 and P14 are allocated based on their 61% contribution and 39% to the total revenue (Table 14).

Table 14 Economic Allocation for P13 and P14.

Co-products	Price (€/t)	Production (t)	Annual Revenue (€)	Allocation (%)
P13	35	575822.79	20153797.71	61%
P14	380	28791.14	10,940,633.04	39%

5. Results and discussion

5.1. Results impact contributions per product

The following section describes the primary factors contributing to the environmental impacts associated with each fertiliser produced by the five companies analysed. The following impact categories are considered: Acidification (AC), Climate change (CC), Ecotoxicity: freshwater (ETfw), Energy resources: non-renewable (ERnr), Eutrophication: freshwater (Eutrfw), Eutrophication: marine (Eutrm), Eutrophication: terrestrial (Eutrt), Human toxicity: carcinogenic (HTc), Human toxicity: non-carcinogenic (HTnc), Ionising radiation: human health (Irhh), Land use (LU), Material resources: metals/minerals (Teae), Ozone depletion (OD), Particulate matter formation (Pmf), Photochemical oxidant formation: human health (POFhh), Water use (WU) (Table 1).

5.1.1 Company A (P1, P2, P3, P4 and P5)

In general, the raw material quicklime is the primary contributor to most environmental impact categories across all fertilisers except P1. For P1, the main contributors to overall impact are the raw materials urea and KCl (Figure 16).

Figure 16. Impact contributions of P1.

The addition of quicklime P2, P3, P4 and P5, considering the impacts from its production, accounts for over 85% of climate change impacts (CC), over 65% of acidification (AC), and over 70% of eutrophication (Eutrfw, Eutrm and Eutrt) across these fertilisers. When including the environmental impacts from transporting quicklime, its total contribution rises to over 90% in these categories. Quicklime is the main contributor because its production is highly energy-intensive and emits significant amounts of greenhouse gases, both from the combustion of fossil fuels but also the release of CO₂ from the chemical reaction of the calcination of limestone.

When comparing P2 with P4 and P3 with P5, which have similar production processes except that some quicklime is replaced with ash, there is a small reduction in quicklime's impact, which is balanced by the environmental burden of transporting the ash. For example, quicklime's contribution to climate change (CC) in P2 is 90%, while in P4 it is 88% with ash transport

contributing 3%. Similarly, in P3, quicklime accounts for 90.5% of the impact, but in P5 it reduces to 87%, with ash transport contributing 3% (Figure 17).

Figure 17. Impact contributions of P2 (A), P3 (B), P4 (C) and P5 (D).

5.1.2 Company B (P6)

In Product 6, natural gas was the primary contributor to most impact categories, mainly due to emissions from its production, and specifically in the climate change (CC) category, due to estimated emissions from its combustion. This is primarily due to the significant impacts associated with its production, including the methane leakage across its lifecycle (Howarth, 2014).

Sulfuric acid used in the production of Product 6 contributes more than 20% to the impacts in Water Use (WU), Particulate Matter Formation (Pmf), and Material Resources: Metals/Minerals (Teae), and over 10% in the Acidification (AC) category (Figure 18). These impacts are linked to the energy-intensive production of sulfuric acid, which has a high water consumption and air pollutant emissions.

Figure 18. Impact contributions of P6.

5.1.3 Company C (P7, P8, P9 and P10)

In Product 7, the transport of the slaked lime is the main contributor in all impact categories, contributing over 80% in each, except for the impact category climate change (CC), where combustion-related emissions from light fuel and volatized emissions from the application of slaked lime are the primary contributors. In this case, since the lime added was considered a residue because it is burnt lime, no environmental burden is allocated to its production, making transportation the main source of impacts (Figure 19).

Figure 19. Impact contributions of P7.

In Product 8, which uses no additional raw material, the transport of the mixed sludge was clearly the biggest contributor to all the impact categories. Combustion-related and from light fuel combustion also played a role in the Climate Change (CC) impact category. The light fuel oil had a minor contribution to the different impact categories (Figure 20).

Figure 20. Impact contributions of P8.

In P9 (Figure 21), the impact is almost entirely attributed to the concentrated potato cell sap, as this raw material was not considered a waste, as it has economic value, and the environmental footprint of its production must be accounted for. The fertiliser is produced exclusively from this by-product without any additional raw materials, which represents a significant quantity of input required. Although an economic allocation was applied to distribute the impacts of the production between the primary product (potato starch) and its by-product (potato cell sap), the associated impacts are high. This is due to the high volume of potato sap generated; approximately 5 tons of potato cell sap are byproducts from 1t of potato starch (Li & Zhang, 2010). As a result, 5.67% of the environmental impacts are allocated to the concentrated potato cell sap and 94.33% to the potato starch.

Figure 21. Impact contributions of P9

In P10, the impact is more distributed between the transport and the raw material. In this case, the amount of vinasse as byproduct from the production of yeast is less, 2.33 t of vinasse per 1 t of yeast produced (Lisičar-Vukušić et al., 2019), leading to an allocation of the impacts of 0.33% to the concentrated vinasse and 99.67% to the primary product.

Figure 22. Impact Contributions of P10

5.1.4 Company D (P11 and P12)

The Impact Contribution are similarly distributed for the production P11 and P12, as they follow the same production steps. In both cases, the main impact contributors are sawdust and biochar across all impact categories.

The main differences between P11 and P12 are the environmental burden associated with biochar. In the production of P11, it is added 98 grams of biochar are added per kilogram of product, while in the production of P12 is added 53 grams of biochar are added per product (Figure 23).

A)

Figure 23. Impact contributions of P11 (A) and P12 (B).

5.1.5 Company E (P13, P14 and P15)

In Products 13 and 14, the addition of polyacrylamide and the electricity for separating the liquid and solid fraction (L-S) and the electricity for the flotation process clearly made up the main contributions across the impact categories (Figure 24). Sulfuric acid contributed only minimally to the impacts, with the highest contributions in Acidification (AC) and Water Use (WU).

Figure 24. Impact contributions of P13 and P14.

In product 15, polyacrylamide and electricity for bio-drying are the main contributors to all impact categories (Figure 25).

When comparing the three fertilisers, we notice that the impacts associated with the addition of polyacrylamide and electricity used for the separation of the S-L are not equally distributed and are lower for P15. This difference is due to the physical allocation that has been applied for inputs required for the separation process, which is based on the mass of the solid and liquid fraction. As the liquid fraction, which is used for P13 and P14 production, is larger than the solid fraction, which is used for P15 production, a bigger share of the inputs and associated impacts is allocated to the liquid fraction. As a result, P15 has a smaller share of the environmental burden from the separation L-S process.

Figure 25. Impact contributions of P15.

General comments about the impact contribution

Overall, the impact categories were predominantly driven by raw materials in products where non-waste-based inputs (such as quicklime in P2, potato cell sap in P9, vinasse from yeast in P10) were used, as these materials had the largest contributions across most impact categories. Also, when using more traditional raw materials like biochar and sawdust (as in Products 9 and 10), the raw material itself played a significant role in the impact contributions.

However, in some products where mainly waste was used as the input, transport and energy use (natural gas in Product 6, Product 8, electricity for pelletizing in Product 11, or bio-drying in Product 13) emerged as key contributors, particularly in categories related to human health and environmental impacts like particulate matter formation and climate change.

In summary, while raw materials were the primary drivers in many products (Products 2, 3, 9, 10, 11 and 12), transport and energy use were particularly influential in impacting contributions in products with waste as input (Products 4, 7, 8, 13, 14, and 15).

5.2. Overall environmental impact and functional unit discussion

The functional unit (FU) of the fertilisers should quantify the performance of the product system. However, fertilisers are intermediate products to produce a final good (e.g. food product), and it is more difficult to define the FU because they can fulfil multiple functions and the whole life cycle of the product, such as the application of the fertiliser, is not known. For this reason, the following section examines the impact of contributions results using different FUs: the declared functional unit of 1 kg of fertiliser and the nutrient-based functional units of kg of N, P₂O₅, and K₂O.

5.2.1 Functional unit: mass of fertiliser

As described in Table 15, when using the declared functional unit (1kg of fertiliser), P8 and P7 exhibit notably low environmental impacts across most categories. P8 is the most environmentally favourable, achieving minimal values in the majority of impact categories, including climate change (8.46×10^{-4} kg CO₂-eq) and acidification (1.38×10^{-6} mol H⁺-eq). The production of P7 and P8 uses waste as a primary raw material, and the process is not energy-intensive, as it only requires a wheel loader to mix the raw materials.

In contrast, P9, which is produced by the same company, has the highest environmental impact in most impact categories. This is because this fertiliser is produced entirely from a by-product with economic value, so it was not classified as waste, and the impacts of the production of this raw material are counted. Even though an economic allocation has been applied to distribute the impacts between the main product and this by-product, the impacts remain high due to the large quantity of material used for producing the fertiliser. However, since no data on by-product processing was available, the economic allocation may not be accurate and lead to an overestimation of the environmental impacts.

In the climate change impact category, P11 produces the highest greenhouse gas emissions among all alternative fertilising products analysed, with a value of 2.05×10^{-1} kg CO₂-eq. This elevated impact is primarily attributed to the addition of biochar derived from apple cultivation residues. However, it is important to note that in this case, there was neither specific primary data regarding the biochar production process from apple residues, nor was this data accessible in the Ecoinvent database. As a result, a proxy dataset for charcoal produced from timber was used to model this component. This substitution may overestimate the actual environmental burden, as timber-based charcoal typically produces higher carbon emissions. Inclusion of primary data or a more representative life cycle inventory specific to apple-derived biochar could lead to a more accurate and potentially lower climate change impact for P11. In comparison, P12 demonstrates improved environmental performance in this category, with a significantly lower impact of 1.34×10^{-1} kg CO₂-eq, partly due to its reduced biochar content in comparison with P11.

An important limitation of the PEF methodology herein follows, and the LCA limitation in the accounting of the ecosystem's services provided by the addition of a carbon amendment apart from the plant nutrients. Some of the advantages of an initiative to merge both methods were described in the NOVAFERT deliverable 2.1 (Novafert, 2024).

5.2.2 Functional unit: mass of nutrient content (N, P₂O and K₂O) of the fertiliser

The alternative fertilising products differ both physically and chemically and present the emissions per 1 kg as FU was limited to the final aim of PEF, that is, their comparability. As alternative fertilising products are to some extent NPK fertilisers, it was used a FU based on nutrient content (Egas et al. 2023). Table 16 presents the NPK profile for each product, including the nutrient concentrations per kilogram of fertiliser

Considering the NPK composition of the fertilisers, the environmental impacts are evaluated per kilogram of N, P₂O₅ and K₂O supplied (Annexe II). The results are normalised and presented relative to the maximum value within each impact category among the alternative fertilising products, considering the maximum value per impact category among products (Table 15)

The most nutrient-dense products are P14 for N, P6 for P₂O₅, and P1 for K₂O. However, high nutrient concentration does not necessarily mean superior environmental performance per kilogram of nutrient. In fact, these products do not consistently show the lowest environmental impacts across categories.

In general, when using a nutrient-based FU, P8 continues demonstrating the lowest environmental impacts across all categories for both N and P₂O₅. In contrast, P4 demonstrates better performance when K₂O is the focus. This can be attributed to its significantly higher K₂O content in P4, which is approximately 36 times greater than that of P8.

Moreover, the ranking of fertilisers with the worst environmental performance varies considerably depending on which nutrient was used as the reference for comparison. For example, P3 has the highest environmental impact when impacts are calculated per unit of P₂O₅ and shows relatively high impact when assessed per unit of K₂O.

These findings show the importance of selecting a functional unit that reflects the intended use of the fertiliser. An alternative fertilising product that appears less favourable when assessed by one nutrient may perform better when evaluated by another. As a result, selecting the most environmentally efficient option depends on the specific nutrient target, making it essential to align fertiliser choice with agronomic needs

Table 15. Impact Contributions of fertilisers (FU: 1kg fertiliser)

Impact category	Unit	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15
AC	mol H+-Eq	5.11E-04	8.79E-05	1.52E-04	7.37E-05	7.63E-05	1.45E-04	1.66E-05	1.38E-06	1.64E-03	1.74E-04	4.45E-04	3.55E-04	6.70E-04	3.64E-04	1.99E-04
CC	kg CO2-Eq	1.36E-01	7.43E-02	8.30E-02	5.16E-02	5.21E-02	1.44E-01	6.64E-03	8.46E-04	1.00E-01	3.70E-02	2.05E-01	1.34E-01	1.06E-01	5.73E-02	4.46E-02
ETfw	CTUe	3.54E+00	1.09E-01	1.50E-01	7.61E-02	7.94E-02	1.11E-01	1.21E-02	2.22E-03	3.61E+00	4.91E-01	3.47E-01	2.75E-01	9.85E-01	5.35E-01	2.43E-01
ERnr	MJ, net calorific value	2.25E+00	3.78E-01	6.68E-01	2.69E-01	2.76E-01	2.07E+00	4.48E-02	8.02E-03	9.73E-01	4.56E-01	1.37E+00	1.19E+00	2.60E+00	1.41E+00	1.34E+00
Eutrfw	kg P-Eq	1.84E-05	2.07E-06	4.21E-06	1.46E-06	1.51E-06	1.49E-06	2.17E-07	3.86E-08	5.26E-05	3.75E-06	2.90E-05	2.43E-05	1.85E-05	1.00E-05	6.52E-06
Eutrm	kg N-Eq	1.11E-04	1.87E-05	3.51E-05	1.94E-05	2.05E-05	3.52E-05	5.52E-06	2.85E-07	8.80E-04	5.58E-05	1.31E-04	1.04E-04	1.99E-04	1.08E-04	5.91E-05
Eutrt	mol N-Eq	1.46E-03	2.07E-04	3.83E-04	2.14E-04	2.25E-04	3.72E-04	6.03E-05	3.08E-06	6.69E-03	5.75E-04	1.34E-03	1.07E-03	1.33E-03	7.24E-04	4.79E-04
HTc	CTUh	5.57E-10	7.77E-11	1.06E-10	5.61E-11	5.93E-11	1.72E-10	2.12E-11	4.05E-12	7.06E-10	2.25E-10	3.59E-10	3.08E-10	4.98E-10	2.71E-10	1.61E-10
HTnc	CTUh	1.21E-09	1.93E-10	3.82E-10	1.43E-10	1.48E-10	1.34E-10	3.27E-11	5.24E-12	5.25E-09	3.35E-10	8.26E-10	6.42E-10	7.86E-10	4.27E-10	3.06E-10
Irhh	kBq U235-Eq	4.89E-03	6.38E-04	1.12E-02	4.99E-04	4.96E-04	2.46E-04	6.66E-05	1.09E-05	3.13E-03	7.53E-04	2.31E-02	2.17E-02	5.80E-02	3.15E-02	4.24E-02
LU	dimensionless	6.43E-01	9.01E-02	1.65E-01	7.83E-02	8.37E-02	2.11E-02	3.35E-02	4.84E-03	5.34E+00	3.72E+00	4.75E+01	3.80E+01	3.65E-01	1.98E-01	1.84E-01
Teae	kg Sb-Eq	1.32E-06	2.15E-07	4.08E-07	1.48E-07	1.49E-07	2.53E-08	9.97E-09	1.90E-09	9.84E-07	1.35E-07	2.14E-07	1.78E-07	6.26E-07	3.40E-07	1.94E-07
OD	kg CFC-11-Eq	3.89E-09	4.46E-10	6.19E-10	3.19E-10	3.27E-10	4.13E-09	6.88E-11	1.18E-11	3.87E-09	6.37E-10	1.14E-09	1.01E-09	1.97E-09	1.07E-09	8.22E-10
Pmf	disease incidence	7.64E-09	8.63E-10	1.25E-09	7.57E-10	8.10E-10	5.17E-10	3.22E-10	4.34E-11	1.28E-08	2.79E-09	5.25E-09	4.23E-09	5.06E-09	2.75E-09	1.36E-09
POFhh	kg NMVOC-Eq	4.92E-04	1.11E-04	1.63E-04	9.51E-05	9.88E-05	2.37E-04	2.22E-05	2.02E-06	5.06E-04	1.40E-04	1.07E-03	7.12E-04	3.64E-04	1.98E-04	1.51E-04
WU	m3 world Eq deprived	1.89E-01	1.72E-03	7.53E-03	1.25E-03	1.29E-03	2.73E-03	2.24E-04	3.92E-05	7.63E-01	1.00E-02	1.29E-01	8.90E-02	6.38E-02	3.46E-02	2.53E-02

Table 16. NPK Profile for each fertiliser (P1-P15).

NPK PROFILE	Unit	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15
Nitrogen	kg nitrogen/ kg fertiliser	0.1540	0.0160	0.0110	0.0160	0.0120	0.1276	0.0065	0.0033	0.0476	0.0358	0.0296	0.2619	0.0378
Phosphorus (P ₂ O ₅)	kg P ₂ O ₅ / kg fertiliser	0.0412	0.0275	0.0275	0.0412	0.0321	0.1031	0.0029	0.0014	0.0098	0.0080	0.0015	No P ₂ O ₅	0.0090
Potassium (K ₂ O)	kg K ₂ O/ kg fertiliser	0.2168	0.0024	0.0036	0.0361	0.0108	0.0651	0.0003	0.0001	0.0114	0.0106	0.0288	No K ₂ O	0.0068

Functional Unit: 1kg BBF

Impact category	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15
AC	0.31	0.05	0.09	0.04	0.05	0.09	0.01	0.00	1.00	0.11	0.27	0.22	0.41	0.22	0.12
CC	0.66	0.36	0.41	0.25	0.25	0.70	0.03	0.00	0.49	0.18	1.00	0.66	0.52	0.28	0.22
ETfw	0.98	0.03	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.14	0.10	0.08	0.27	0.15	0.07
ERnr	0.86	0.15	0.26	0.10	0.11	0.80	0.02	0.00	0.37	0.18	0.53	0.46	1.00	0.54	0.52
Eutrfw	0.35	0.04	0.08	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.07	0.55	0.46	0.35	0.19	0.12
Eutrm	0.13	0.02	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.01	0.00	1.00	0.06	0.15	0.12	0.23	0.12	0.07
Eutrt	0.22	0.03	0.06	0.03	0.03	0.06	0.01	0.00	1.00	0.09	0.20	0.16	0.20	0.11	0.07
HTc	0.79	0.11	0.15	0.08	0.08	0.24	0.03	0.01	1.00	0.32	0.51	0.44	0.71	0.38	0.23
HTnc	0.23	0.04	0.07	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.00	1.00	0.06	0.16	0.12	0.15	0.08	0.06
Irh	0.08	0.01	0.19	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.01	0.40	0.37	1.00	0.54	0.73
LU	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.11	0.08	1.00	0.80	0.01	0.00	0.00
Teae	1.00	0.16	0.31	0.11	0.11	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.75	0.10	0.16	0.14	0.48	0.26	0.15
OD	0.94	0.11	0.15	0.08	0.08	1.00	0.02	0.00	0.94	0.15	0.28	0.24	0.48	0.26	0.20
Pmf	0.60	0.07	0.10	0.06	0.06	0.04	0.03	0.00	1.00	0.22	0.41	0.33	0.39	0.21	0.11
POFhh	0.46	0.10	0.15	0.09	0.09	0.22	0.02	0.00	0.47	0.13	1.00	0.66	0.34	0.18	0.14
WU	0.25	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.01	0.17	0.12	0.08	0.05	0.03

Functional Unit: 1 kg of Nitrogen

Impact category	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15
AC	0.02	0.03	0.08	0.03	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.00	1.00	0.03	0.06	0.06	0.14	0.01	0.03
CC	0.09	0.46	0.75	0.32	0.43	0.11	0.10	0.03	1.00	0.11	0.43	0.37	0.36	0.02	0.12
ETfw	0.06	0.02	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.00	1.00	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.09	0.01	0.02
ERnr	0.15	0.24	0.62	0.17	0.24	0.17	0.07	0.02	1.00	0.14	0.30	0.34	0.90	0.06	0.36
Eutrfw	0.02	0.02	0.07	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.00	1.00	0.02	0.12	0.13	0.12	0.01	0.03
Eutrm	0.01	0.01	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.00	1.00	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.08	0.00	0.02
Eutrt	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.02	0.03	0.00	0.01	0.00	1.00	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.07	0.00	0.02
HTc	0.05	0.07	0.14	0.05	0.07	0.02	0.05	0.02	1.00	0.10	0.11	0.12	0.24	0.01	0.06
HTnc	0.01	0.02	0.07	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.00	1.00	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.05	0.00	0.02
Irh	0.02	0.02	0.52	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.16	0.01	0.25	0.31	1.00	0.06	0.57
LU	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.50	0.11	0.94	1.00	0.01	0.00	0.00
Teae	0.09	0.14	0.38	0.09	0.13	0.00	0.02	0.01	1.00	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.21	0.01	0.05
OD	0.07	0.07	0.15	0.05	0.07	0.08	0.03	0.01	1.00	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.17	0.01	0.06
Pmf	0.04	0.04	0.09	0.04	0.05	0.00	0.04	0.01	1.00	0.07	0.09	0.09	0.13	0.01	0.03
POFhh	0.06	0.14	0.29	0.12	0.16	0.04	0.07	0.01	1.00	0.08	0.45	0.39	0.24	0.01	0.08
WU	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.00	0.01

Functional Unit: 1 kg of Phosphorus (P₂O₅)

Impact category	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15
AC	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.36	No P ₂ O ₅	0.10	0.10	1.00	No P ₂ O ₅	0.05
CC	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.14	No P ₂ O ₅	0.31	0.25	1.00	No P ₂ O ₅	0.07
ETfw	0.13	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.54	No P ₂ O ₅	0.06	0.05	1.00	No P ₂ O ₅	0.04
ERnr	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.05	No P ₂ O ₅	0.08	0.09	1.00	No P ₂ O ₅	0.09
Eutrfw	0.04	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.42	No P ₂ O ₅	0.25	0.25	1.00	No P ₂ O ₅	0.06
Eutrm	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.65	No P ₂ O ₅	0.10	0.10	1.00	No P ₂ O ₅	0.05
Eutrt	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.74	No P ₂ O ₅	0.16	0.16	1.00	No P ₂ O ₅	0.06
HTc	0.04	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.21	No P ₂ O ₅	0.11	0.12	1.00	No P ₂ O ₅	0.06
HTnc	0.06	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.98	No P ₂ O ₅	0.17	0.16	1.00	No P ₂ O ₅	0.07
Irh	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	No P ₂ O ₅	0.06	0.07	1.00	No P ₂ O ₅	0.13
LU	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10	No P ₂ O ₅	1.00	0.98	0.05	No P ₂ O ₅	0.00
Teae	0.08	0.02	0.04	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.23	No P ₂ O ₅	0.05	0.05	1.00	No P ₂ O ₅	0.05
OD	0.07	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.29	No P ₂ O ₅	0.09	0.10	1.00	No P ₂ O ₅	0.07
Pmf	0.06	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.03	0.01	0.37	No P ₂ O ₅	0.16	0.16	1.00	No P ₂ O ₅	0.05
POFhh	0.05	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.20	No P ₂ O ₅	0.47	0.38	1.00	No P ₂ O ₅	0.07
WU	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	No P ₂ O ₅	0.18	0.15	0.57	No P ₂ O ₅	0.04

Functional Unit: 1 kg of Potassium (K₂O)

Impact category	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15
AC	0.05	0.72	0.82	0.04	0.14	0.04	1.00	0.23	0.89	0.04	0.77	0.66	0.46	No K ₂ O	0.58
CC	0.02	1.00	0.74	0.05	0.16	0.07	0.66	0.23	0.09	0.01	0.58	0.41	0.12	No K ₂ O	0.21
ETfw	0.16	0.45	0.42	0.02	0.07	0.02	0.37	0.18	1.00	0.05	0.31	0.26	0.34	No K ₂ O	0.36
ERnr	0.05	0.79	0.94	0.04	0.13	0.16	0.70	0.34	0.14	0.02	0.61	0.57	0.46	No K ₂ O	1.00
Eutrfw	0.03	0.34	0.46	0.02	0.05	0.01	0.26	0.13	0.57	0.02	1.00	0.90	0.25	No K ₂ O	0.38
Eutrm	0.02	0.32	0.40	0.02	0.08	0.02	0.70	0.10	1.00	0.02	0.47	0.40	0.28	No K ₂ O	0.36
Eutrt	0.04	0.46	0.57	0.03	0.11	0.03	1.00	0.14	1.00	0.03	0.64	0.55	0.25	No K ₂ O	0.38
HTc	0.04	0.49	0.45	0.02	0.08	0.04	1.00	0.51	0.30	0.04	0.48	0.45	0.27	No K ₂ O	0.36
HTnc	0.04	0.55	0.73	0.03	0.09	0.01	0.69	0.30	1.00	0.02	0.50	0.42	0.19	No K ₂ O	0.31
Irh	0.00	0.04	0.50	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.33	0.33	0.32	No K ₂ O	1.00
LU	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.04	0.01	1.00	0.86	0.00	No K ₂ O	0.01
Teae	0.05	0.79	1.00	0.04	0.12	0.00	0.27	0.14	0.24	0.01	0.17	0.15	0.19	No K ₂ O	0.25
OD	0.08	0.88	0.81	0.04	0.14	0.30	1.00	0.46	0.51	0.03	0.47	0.45	0.32	No K ₂ O	0.57
Pmf	0.04	0.36	0.35	0.02	0.08	0.01	1.00	0.36	0.36	0.03	0.47	0.40	0.18	No K ₂ O	0.20
POFhh	0.02	0.49	0.48	0.03	0.10	0.04	0.72	0.18	0.15	0.02	1.00	0.71	0.13	No K ₂ O	0.24
WU	0.04	0.03	0.10	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.03	0.02	1.00	0.01	0.54	0.40	0.11	No K ₂ O	0.18

Figure 26. Normalised Impact Contributions of fertilisers across different Functional Units.

5.3. Sensitivity Analysis for the Economic Allocation

When handling multi-functional processes, where a production process delivers several products ('co-products'), the study used economic allocation methods. In these situations, the inputs and emissions linked to the processes were portioned between the co-products. The following sensitivity analysis tests the allocation methods used for P6, P13 and P14, to assess how variations in the economic allocation influence the overall results.

5.3.1 Economic Allocation for P6

The price of P6 was unknown. Therefore, an economic allocation was applied by estimating its value based on the typical market price of compost used in industrial processes.

Alternatively, we test in this sensitivity analysis a price for P6, based on its NPK content and the market prices of equivalent inorganic fertilisers that it may substitute. The estimated price is presented in Table 17, along with its potential contribution to the total annual revenue of Company B.

Table 17. Economic Allocation Adjustment for P6 in Sensitivity Analysis

Co-products	Price	Price Units	Annual Production (AP)	AP Units	Annual Revenue €/year	% of Total Annual Revenue
Electricity	0.17 €	€/kWh	98019485	kWh/year	16,640,522.92	98.30%
N	0.473 €	€/kg	377.9512	t/year	178,770.92	1.06%
P (as P ₂ O ₅)	0.241 €	€/kg	305.4162811	t/year	73,605.32	0.43%
K (as K ₂ O)	0.188€	€/kg	192.682311	t/year	36,224.27	0.21%
P6 as total NPK	0.097 €	€/kg P6	2962	t/year	288,600.52	1.70%

The environmental impact attributed to P6 was allocated based on a 1.70% contribution to the annual revenue, as opposed to the original 0.61%. As shown in Figure 27, this updated economic allocation increases the environmental impacts of P6, resulting in its being ranked as having the worst performance in terms of both Climate change impact, Energy resources: non-renewable and Material resources: metals/minerals.

RESULTS BEFORE SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS (P6)

Impact Contributions (Functional Unit: 1kg BBF)

Normalized Impact Contributions (Functional Unit: 1kg BBF)

Table with 16 columns (P1-P15) and 20 rows (AC, CC, Etfw, ERnr, Eutrfrw, Eutrm, Eutrt, HTc, HTnc, Irhh, LU, Teae, OD, Pmf, POFhh, WU) showing impact contributions before sensitivity analysis.

Table with 16 columns (P1-P15) and 20 rows (AC, CC, Etfw, ERnr, Eutrfrw, Eutrm, Eutrt, HTc, HTnc, Irhh, LU, Teae, OD, Pmf, POFhh, WU) showing normalized impact contributions before sensitivity analysis.

RESULTS FROM SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS (P6)

Impact Contributions (Functional Unit: 1kg BBF)

Normalized Impact Contributions (Functional Unit: 1kg BBF)

Table with 16 columns (P1-P15) and 20 rows (AC, CC, Etfw, ERnr, Eutrfrw, Eutrm, Eutrt, HTc, HTnc, Irhh, LU, Teae, OD, Pmf, POFhh, WU) showing impact contributions after sensitivity analysis.

Table with 16 columns (P1-P15) and 20 rows (AC, CC, Etfw, ERnr, Eutrfrw, Eutrm, Eutrt, HTc, HTnc, Irhh, LU, Teae, OD, Pmf, POFhh, WU) showing normalized impact contributions after sensitivity analysis.

Figure 27. Comparison of Results Before and After the sensitivity analysis for P6

5.3.2 Economic Allocation for P9 and P10

There was no primary data available on the processing of the raw products used for producing P9 and P10, as these are in concentrated forms of byproducts; this study estimates the concentration rates based on the NPK content of the by-product and the final fertiliser. An economic allocation was performed considering the concentration rate of these raw materials, but this one could vary. This sensitivity analysis tests the outcomes of the results using diverse concentration rates (Table 18).

Table 18. Economic Allocation Adjustment for P9 and P10 in Sensitivity Analysis

Product	Raw material	Concentration rate	Economic Allocation of the Impact
P9 (Baseline)	Main product: Potato starch	3.33 estimated by comparing N content from by-product to final fertiliser (Li & Zhang, 2010)	94.33%
	By-product: Concentrated potato cell sap		5.67%
p9 (Sensitivity Analysis)	Main product: Potato starch	6.02 estimated by comparing the K content from the by-product to the final fertiliser (Li & Zhang, 2010)	96.78%
	By-product: Concentrated potato cell sap		3.22%
P10 (Baseline)	Main product: Fodder yeast	19.41 estimated by comparing N content from by-product to final fertiliser (Gómez & Correa, 2024)	99.67%
	By-product: Concentrated vinasse		0.33%
P10 (Sensitivity Analysis)	Main product: Fodder yeast	11.67 estimated by comparing dry matter content from by-product to concentrated vinasse (Gómez & Correa, 2024)	99.45%
	By-product: Concentrated vinasse		0.55%

The higher concentration rate of the by-product in P9 and the smaller allocation of the impact that results, lead to a reduction of the environmental impacts. Consequently, as shown in Figure 28, the product with the highest environmental burden changes in several impact categories: Freshwater Ecotoxicity, Human Toxicity (carcinogenic), and Particulate Matter Formation. In contrast, the smaller concentration rate in P10 and the corresponding larger allocation of the impact result in increased environmental burdens.

This sensitivity analysis shows the importance of having accurate and specific data on the production of the raw materials used in the production process. Without information of the life cycle inventory of these inputs, particularly by-products with an economic value not commonly used in other industrial processes, there could be an inaccurate assessment of the product's environmental performance.

RESULTS BEFORE SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS (P9, P10)

Impact Contributions (Functional Unit: 1kg BBF)

Impact category	Unit	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15
AC	mol H ⁺ -Eq	5.11E-04	8.79E-05	1.52E-04	7.37E-05	7.63E-05	1.45E-04	1.66E-05	1.38E-06	1.64E-03	1.74E-04	4.45E-04	3.55E-04	6.70E-04	3.64E-04	1.99E-04
CC	kg CO ₂ -Eq	1.36E-01	7.43E-02	8.30E-02	5.16E-02	5.21E-02	1.44E-01	6.64E-03	8.46E-04	1.00E-01	3.70E-02	2.05E-01	1.34E-01	1.06E-01	5.73E-02	4.46E-02
ETfw	CTUe	3.54E+00	1.09E-01	1.50E-01	7.61E-02	7.94E-02	1.11E-01	1.21E-02	2.22E-03	3.61E+00	4.91E-01	3.47E-01	2.75E-01	9.85E-01	5.35E-01	2.43E-01
ERnr	MJ _{net} calorific value	2.25E+00	3.78E-01	6.68E-01	2.69E-01	2.76E-01	2.07E+00	4.48E-02	8.02E-03	9.73E-01	4.56E-01	1.37E+00	1.19E+00	2.60E+00	1.41E+00	1.34E+00
Eutrfw	kg P-Eq	1.84E-05	2.07E-06	4.21E-06	1.46E-06	1.51E-06	1.49E-06	2.17E-07	3.86E-08	5.26E-05	3.75E-06	2.90E-05	2.43E-05	1.85E-05	1.00E-05	6.52E-06
Eutrm	kg N-Eq	1.11E-04	1.87E-05	3.51E-05	1.94E-05	2.05E-05	3.52E-05	5.52E-06	2.85E-07	8.80E-04	5.58E-05	1.31E-04	1.04E-04	1.99E-04	1.08E-04	5.91E-05
Eutrt	mol N-Eq	1.46E-03	2.07E-04	3.83E-04	2.14E-04	2.25E-04	3.72E-04	6.03E-05	3.08E-06	6.69E-03	5.75E-04	1.34E-03	1.07E-03	1.33E-03	7.24E-04	4.79E-04
HTc	CTUh	5.57E-10	7.77E-11	1.06E-10	5.61E-11	5.93E-11	1.72E-10	2.12E-11	4.05E-12	7.06E-10	2.25E-10	3.59E-10	3.08E-10	4.98E-10	2.71E-10	1.61E-10
HTnc	CTUh	1.21E-09	1.93E-10	3.82E-10	1.43E-10	1.48E-10	1.34E-10	3.27E-11	5.24E-12	5.25E-09	3.35E-10	8.26E-10	6.42E-10	7.86E-10	4.27E-10	3.06E-10
lrhh	kBq U235-Eq	4.89E-03	6.38E-04	1.12E-02	4.99E-04	4.96E-04	2.46E-04	6.66E-05	1.09E-05	3.13E-03	7.53E-04	2.31E-02	2.17E-02	5.80E-02	3.15E-02	4.24E-02
LU	dimensionless	6.43E-01	9.01E-02	1.65E-01	7.83E-02	8.37E-02	2.11E-02	3.35E-02	4.84E-03	5.34E+00	3.72E+00	4.75E+01	3.80E+01	3.65E-01	1.98E-01	1.84E-01
Teae	kg Sb-Eq	1.32E-06	2.15E-07	4.08E-07	1.48E-07	1.49E-07	2.53E-08	9.97E-09	1.90E-09	9.84E-07	1.35E-07	2.14E-07	1.78E-07	6.26E-07	3.40E-07	1.94E-07
OD	kg CFC-11-Eq	3.89E-09	4.46E-10	6.19E-10	3.19E-10	3.27E-10	4.13E-09	6.88E-11	1.18E-11	3.87E-09	6.37E-10	1.14E-09	1.01E-09	1.97E-09	1.07E-09	8.22E-10
Pmf	disease incidence	7.64E-09	8.63E-10	1.25E-09	7.57E-10	8.10E-10	5.17E-10	3.22E-10	4.34E-11	1.28E-08	2.79E-09	5.25E-09	4.23E-09	5.06E-09	2.75E-09	1.36E-09
POFhh	kg NMVOC-Eq	4.92E-04	1.11E-04	1.63E-04	9.51E-05	9.88E-05	2.37E-04	2.22E-05	2.02E-06	5.06E-04	1.40E-04	1.07E-03	7.12E-04	3.64E-04	1.98E-04	1.51E-04
WU	m ³ world Eq deprived	1.89E-01	1.72E-03	7.53E-03	1.25E-03	1.29E-03	2.73E-03	2.24E-04	3.92E-05	7.63E-01	1.00E-02	1.29E-01	8.90E-02	6.38E-02	3.46E-02	2.53E-02

Normalized Impact Contributions (Functional Unit: 1kg BBF)

Impact category	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15
AC	0.31	0.05	0.09	0.04	0.05	0.09	0.01	0.00	1.00	0.11	0.27	0.22	0.41	0.22	0.12
CC	0.66	0.36	0.41	0.25	0.25	0.70	0.03	0.00	0.49	1.00	0.66	0.52	0.28	0.22	0.22
ETfw	0.98	0.03	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.14	0.10	0.08	0.27	0.15	0.07
ERnr	0.86	0.15	0.26	0.10	0.11	0.80	0.02	0.00	0.37	0.18	0.53	0.46	1.00	0.54	0.52
Eutrfw	0.35	0.04	0.08	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.07	0.55	0.46	0.35	0.19	0.12
Eutrm	0.13	0.02	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.01	0.00	1.00	0.06	0.15	0.12	0.23	0.12	0.07
Eutrt	0.22	0.03	0.06	0.03	0.03	0.06	0.01	0.00	1.00	0.09	0.20	0.16	0.20	0.11	0.07
HTc	0.79	0.11	0.15	0.08	0.08	0.24	0.03	0.01	1.00	0.32	0.51	0.44	0.71	0.38	0.23
HTnc	0.23	0.04	0.07	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.00	1.00	0.06	0.16	0.12	0.15	0.08	0.06
lrhh	0.08	0.01	0.19	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.01	0.40	0.37	1.00	0.54	0.73
LU	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.11	0.08	1.00	0.80	0.01	0.00	0.00
Teae	1.00	0.16	0.31	0.11	0.11	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.75	0.10	0.16	0.14	0.48	0.26	0.15
OD	0.94	0.11	0.15	0.08	0.08	1.00	0.02	0.00	0.94	0.15	0.28	0.24	0.48	0.26	0.20
Pmf	0.60	0.07	0.10	0.06	0.06	0.04	0.03	0.00	1.00	0.22	0.41	0.33	0.39	0.21	0.11
POFhh	0.46	0.10	0.15	0.09	0.09	0.22	0.02	0.00	0.47	0.13	1.00	0.66	0.34	0.18	0.14
WU	0.25	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.01	0.17	0.12	0.08	0.05	0.03

RESULTS FROM SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS (P9, P10)

Impact Contributions (Functional Unit: 1kg BBF)

Impact category	Unit	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15
AC	mol H ⁺ -Eq	5.11E-04	8.79E-05	1.52E-04	7.37E-05	7.63E-05	1.45E-04	1.66E-05	1.38E-06	9.33E-04	2.35E-04	4.45E-04	3.55E-04	6.70E-04	3.64E-04	1.99E-04
CC	kg CO ₂ -Eq	1.36E-01	7.43E-02	8.30E-02	5.16E-02	5.21E-02	1.44E-01	6.64E-03	8.46E-04	5.71E-02	4.30E-02	2.05E-01	1.34E-01	1.06E-01	5.73E-02	4.46E-02
ETfw	CTUe	3.54E+00	1.09E-01	1.50E-01	7.61E-02	7.94E-02	1.11E-01	1.21E-02	2.22E-03	2.05E+00	7.42E-01	3.47E-01	2.75E-01	9.85E-01	5.35E-01	2.43E-01
ERnr	MJ _{net} calorific value	2.25E+00	3.78E-01	6.68E-01	2.69E-01	2.76E-01	2.07E+00	4.48E-02	8.02E-03	5.55E-01	4.99E-01	1.37E+00	1.19E+00	2.60E+00	1.41E+00	1.34E+00
Eutrfw	kg P-Eq	1.84E-05	2.07E-06	4.21E-06	1.46E-06	1.51E-06	1.49E-06	2.17E-07	3.86E-08	2.99E-05	4.98E-06	2.90E-05	2.43E-05	1.85E-05	1.00E-05	6.52E-06
Eutrm	kg N-Eq	1.11E-04	1.87E-05	3.51E-05	1.94E-05	2.05E-05	3.52E-05	5.52E-06	2.85E-07	5.00E-04	7.91E-05	1.31E-04	1.04E-04	1.99E-04	1.08E-04	5.91E-05
Eutrt	mol N-Eq	1.46E-03	2.07E-04	3.83E-04	2.14E-04	2.25E-04	3.72E-04	6.03E-05	3.08E-06	3.80E-03	8.07E-04	1.34E-03	1.07E-03	1.33E-03	7.24E-04	4.79E-04
HTc	CTUh	5.57E-10	7.77E-11	1.06E-10	5.61E-11	5.93E-11	1.72E-10	2.12E-11	4.05E-12	4.02E-10	2.44E-10	3.59E-10	3.08E-10	4.98E-10	2.71E-10	1.61E-10
HTnc	CTUh	1.21E-09	1.93E-10	3.82E-10	1.43E-10	1.48E-10	1.34E-10	3.27E-11	5.24E-12	2.98E-09	3.92E-10	8.26E-10	6.42E-10	7.86E-10	4.27E-10	3.06E-10
lrhh	kBq U235-Eq	4.89E-03	6.38E-04	1.12E-02	4.99E-04	4.96E-04	2.46E-04	6.66E-05	1.09E-05	1.78E-03	9.20E-04	2.31E-02	2.17E-02	5.80E-02	3.15E-02	4.24E-02
LU	dimensionless	6.43E-01	9.01E-02	1.65E-01	7.83E-02	8.37E-02	2.11E-02	3.35E-02	4.84E-03	3.03E+00	6.00E+00	4.75E+01	3.80E+01	3.65E-01	1.98E-01	1.84E-01
Teae	kg Sb-Eq	1.32E-06	2.15E-07	4.08E-07	1.48E-07	1.49E-07	2.53E-08	9.97E-09	1.90E-09	5.59E-07	1.65E-07	2.14E-07	1.78E-07	6.26E-07	3.40E-07	1.94E-07
OD	kg CFC-11-Eq	3.89E-09	4.46E-10	6.19E-10	3.19E-10	3.27E-10	4.13E-09	6.88E-11	1.18E-11	2.20E-09	6.95E-10	1.14E-09	1.01E-09	1.97E-09	1.07E-09	8.22E-10
Pmf	disease incidence	7.64E-09	8.63E-10	1.25E-09	7.57E-10	8.10E-10	5.17E-10	3.22E-10	4.34E-11	7.30E-09	3.30E-09	5.25E-09	4.23E-09	5.06E-09	2.75E-09	1.36E-09
POFhh	kg NMVOC-Eq	4.92E-04	1.11E-04	1.63E-04	9.51E-05	9.88E-05	2.37E-04	2.22E-05	2.02E-06	2.88E-04	1.57E-04	1.07E-03	7.12E-04	3.64E-04	1.98E-04	1.51E-04
WU	m ³ world Eq deprived	1.89E-01	1.72E-03	7.53E-03	1.25E-03	1.29E-03	2.73E-03	2.24E-04	3.92E-05	4.33E-01	1.54E-02	1.29E-01	8.90E-02	6.38E-02	3.46E-02	2.53E-02

Normalized Impact Contributions (Functional Unit: 1kg BBF)

Impact category	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15
AC	0.55	0.09	0.16	0.08	0.08	0.16	0.02	0.00	1.00	0.25	0.48	0.38	0.72	0.39	0.21
CC	0.66	0.36	0.41	0.25	0.25	0.70	0.03	0.00	0.28	0.21	1.00	0.66	0.52	0.28	0.22
ETfw	1.00	0.03	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.58	0.21	0.10	0.08	0.28	0.15	0.07
ERnr	0.86	0.15	0.26	0.10	0.11	0.80	0.02	0.00	0.21	0.19	0.53	0.46	1.00	0.54	0.52
Eutrfw	0.62	0.07	0.14	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.01	0.00	1.00	0.17	0.97	0.81	0.62	0.34	0.22
Eutrm	0.22	0.04	0.07	0.04	0.04	0.07	0.01	0.00	1.00	0.16	0.26	0.21	0.40	0.22	0.12
Eutrt	0.38	0.05	0.10	0.06	0.06	0.10	0.02	0.00	1.00	0.21	0.35	0.28	0.35	0.19	0.13
HTc	1.00	0.14	0.19	0.10	0.11	0.31	0.04	0.01	0.72	0.44	0.64	0.55	0.90	0.49	0.29
HTnc	0.40	0.06	0.13	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.01	0.00	1.00	0.13	0.28	0.22	0.26	0.14	0.10
lrhh	0.08	0.01	0.19	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.02	0.40	0.37	1.00	0.54	0.73
LU	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.13	1.00	0.80	0.01	0.00	0.00
Teae	1.00	0.16	0.31	0.11	0.11	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.42	0.13	0.16	0.14	0.48	0.26	0.15
OD	0.94	0.11	0.15	0.08	0.08	1.00	0.02	0.00	0.53	0.17	0.28	0.24	0.48	0.26	0.20
Pmf	1.00	0.11	0.16	0.1											

5.3.3 Economic Allocation for P13 and P14

The prices of P13 and P14 were not communicated. They vary among clients. Therefore, an economic allocation was applied by estimating on their value based on the typical market price of its NPK content. The estimated prices are presented in Table 19, along with its potential contribution to the total annual revenue of Company B.

Table 19: Economic allocation Adjustment for P13 and P14 in Sensitivity Analysis

Component	Price (€/kg)	Content (kg/kg)	Revenue for product (€/kg)	% of Revenue
N content	0.473	0.02961	0.014	
P content (as P ₂ O ₅)	0.241	0.00155	0.00037	
K (as K ₂ O)	0.188	0.02876	0.0054	
Estimated price P13 (as total NPK)	0.0198	1.00000	0.020	76.16%
N content	0.473	0.26190	0.062	
P content (as P ₂ O ₅)	0.241	0.00000	No P ₂ O ₅	
K (as K ₂ O)	0.188	0.00000	0.00	
Estimated price P14 (as total NPK)	0.0062	0.05000	6.19	22.84%

The environmental impact attributed to P13 and P14 is now allocated based on a 76.16% and 22.84% respective contribution to the total revenue of the production process, as opposed to the original 64.81% and 35.18%. As shown in Figure 29, this revised economic allocation leads to a higher impact on P13 because it has allocated a higher proportion of the revenue.

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RESULTS BEFORE SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS (P13, P14)

Impact Contributions
(Functional Unit: 1kg BBF)

Normalized Impact Contributions
(Functional Unit: 1kg BBF)

Table with 16 columns (Impact category, Unit, P1-P15) showing impact contributions before sensitivity analysis. Values are in scientific notation.

Table with 16 columns (Impact category, P1-P15) showing normalized impact contributions before sensitivity analysis. Values are in decimal format.

RESULTS FROM SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS (P13, P14)

Impact Contributions
(Functional Unit: 1kg BBF)

Normalized Impact Contributions
(Functional Unit: 1kg BBF)

Table with 16 columns (Impact category, Unit, P1-P15) showing impact contributions after sensitivity analysis. Values are in scientific notation.

Table with 16 columns (Impact category, P1-P15) showing normalized impact contributions after sensitivity analysis. Values are in decimal format.

Figure 29. Comparison of Results Before and After sensitivity analysis for P13 and P14

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The outcome of the sensitivity analysis highlights the influence that economic allocation methods have on the environmental impact results and the subsequent ranking of fertilisers. Economic allocation, which distributes environmental burdens among co-products based on their relative market values, can substantially shift the perceived sustainability of each fertiliser product. When different allocation scenarios are applied, the environmental performance of individual alternative fertilising products may change, sometimes resulting in a reordering of their rankings across various impact categories.

This result demonstrates that the evaluation of alternative fertilising products is highly dependent on the chosen allocation method, demonstrating the importance of considering and clearly reporting allocation approaches when interpreting and comparing results.

5.4. The role of the Circular Footprint Formula in the alternative fertilising products

Table 21 and Figure 30 summarise the results of the CFF to the producer (nutrient recycler) and the consumer in the application. A set of negative results can be observed in the table of the producers. That is because the CFF introduces some credits to nutrient recyclers due to the recovery of the nutrients with a lower impact than the mineral benchmark.

On the other hand, the consumer has an incorporated footprint higher in recycling impact because the credits given to the recyclers have to be neutralised. Therefore, the CFF has a critical point because this can under-incentivise the consumption of alternative fertilising products due to the consumer not getting as many environmental gains in comparison with mineral, even if they are still lower. In this sense, the CFF could be reshaped and more moderate in the division of credits.

It is important to note that this issue arises in situations where the nutrient stream is a waste. In the case of the consumption of secondary raw nutrients as commoditizers, part of the burdens from the economic allocation from the original activity could be split, as in the case of the partial incorporation of the compost (in P3 and P5).

It is important to note that this phenomenon of credits appears only in the circumstances where the environmental impact of the recycling process is higher than the mineral counterparts due to the nutrient content of the alternative fertilising product.

Table 20. Results of Impact Contributions on the consumer side.

Abbr	Units	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15
AC	mol H+ -Eq	2.04E-03	5.62E-04	5.88E-04	7.88E-04	6.08E-04	2.37E-03	9.08E-05	3.88E-05	1.56E-03	4.08E-04	7.61E-04	6.00E-04	7.43E-04	1.66E-03	4.96E-04
CC	kg CO2-Eq	3.24E-01	9.58E-02	9.86E-02	9.55E-02	7.98E-02	3.24E-01	1.35E-02	4.73E-03	1.05E-01	7.86E-02	2.16E-01	1.48E-01	1.18E-01	2.80E-01	7.78E-02
ETfw	CTUe	2.83E+00	8.70E-02	1.20E-01	6.09E-02	6.36E-02	8.88E-02	9.68E-03	1.78E-03	2.89E+00	3.93E-01	2.78E-01	2.20E-01	7.88E-01	4.28E-01	1.94E-01
ERnr	MJ, net calorific value	2.01E+00	3.38E-01	5.67E-01	2.69E-01	2.58E-01	1.87E+00	4.40E-02	1.05E-02	8.03E-01	4.14E-01	1.15E+00	9.93E-01	2.11E+00	1.36E+00	1.11E+00
Eutrfw	kg P-Eq	3.92E-04	2.19E-04	2.20E-04	3.28E-04	2.54E-04	8.38E-04	2.45E-05	1.15E-05	1.30E-04	1.96E-05	1.12E-04	9.13E-05	3.66E-05	7.19E-05	8.47E-05
Eutrm	kg N-Eq	4.22E+00	2.96E-01	3.03E-01	9.47E-01	4.57E-01	2.19E+00	4.51E-02	2.13E-02	6.91E-01	1.60E+00	3.84E-01	3.26E-01	5.52E-01	6.79E-01	2.78E-01
Eutrt	mol N-Eq	3.98E+00	2.34E-01	2.44E-01	8.49E-01	3.87E-01	1.90E+00	3.57E-02	1.67E-02	6.59E-01	1.55E+00	3.35E-01	2.87E-01	5.24E-01	5.24E-01	2.37E-01
HTc	CTUh	2.36E-01	6.18E-02	5.92E-02	9.81E-02	7.06E-02	2.89E-01	9.45E-03	4.57E-03	3.69E-02	4.87E-02	5.01E-02	3.95E-02	2.94E-02	1.55E-01	4.13E-02
HTnc	CTUh	3.06E+00	5.63E-01	5.06E-01	8.45E-01	6.00E-01	3.10E+00	1.18E-01	5.84E-02	3.69E-01	6.84E-01	7.40E-01	5.71E-01	4.66E-01	3.17E+00	5.96E-01
Irhh	kBq U235-Eq	3.99E-03	5.45E-04	8.98E-03	4.51E-04	4.37E-04	3.36E-04	5.75E-05	1.07E-05	2.52E-03	6.10E-04	1.85E-02	1.74E-02	4.64E-02	2.52E-02	3.39E-02
LU	dimensionless	5.15E-01	7.21E-02	1.32E-01	6.27E-02	6.70E-02	1.71E-02	2.68E-02	3.88E-03	4.27E+00	2.98E+00	3.80E+01	3.04E+01	2.92E-01	1.59E-01	1.47E-01
Teae	kg Sb-Eq	3.93E-03	5.24E-04	4.31E-04	7.30E-04	5.07E-04	3.43E-03	1.48E-04	7.43E-05	3.82E-04	9.18E-04	1.02E-03	7.81E-04	6.68E-04	5.04E-03	8.15E-04
Ozone	kg CFC-11-Eq	4.09E-09	6.06E-10	7.33E-10	6.51E-10	5.46E-10	4.48E-09	9.35E-11	2.80E-11	3.25E-09	7.14E-10	1.12E-09	9.69E-10	1.70E-09	1.50E-09	8.27E-10
Pmf	disease incidence	6.15E-09	7.03E-10	1.01E-09	6.25E-10	6.63E-10	4.69E-10	2.59E-10	3.56E-11	1.03E-08	2.24E-09	4.21E-09	3.39E-09	4.05E-09	2.22E-09	1.09E-09
POFhh	kg NMVOC-Eq	3.94E-04	8.86E-05	1.31E-04	7.61E-05	7.90E-05	1.89E-04	1.78E-05	1.62E-06	4.05E-04	1.12E-04	8.60E-04	5.69E-04	2.91E-04	1.58E-04	1.21E-04
WU	m3 world Eq deprived	1.51E-01	1.37E-03	6.02E-03	1.00E-03	1.03E-03	2.18E-03	1.79E-04	3.14E-05	6.10E-01	8.04E-03	1.03E-01	7.12E-02	5.10E-02	2.77E-02	2.03E-02

Table 21. Results of Impact Contributions on the waste generator side.

Abbr	Units	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15
AC	mol H+-Eq	-1.53E-03	-4.74E-04	-4.36E-04	-7.14E-04	-5.32E-04	-2.23E-03	-7.43E-05	-3.74E-05	8.37E-05	-2.34E-04	-3.17E-04	-2.45E-04	-7.31E-05	-1.30E-03	-2.97E-04
CC	kg CO2-Eq	-1.88E-01	-2.15E-02	-1.56E-02	-4.38E-02	-2.77E-02	-1.80E-01	-6.85E-03	-3.88E-03	-4.66E-03	-4.15E-02	-1.17E-02	-1.36E-02	-1.25E-02	-2.23E-01	-3.33E-02
ETfw	CTUe	7.08E-01	2.17E-02	3.00E-02	1.51E-02	1.58E-02	2.20E-02	2.41E-03	4.40E-04	7.22E-01	9.81E-02	6.95E-02	5.50E-02	1.97E-01	1.07E-01	4.85E-02
ERnr	MJ, net calorific value	2.35E-01	3.94E-02	1.02E-01	-2.22E-05	1.73E-02	2.07E-01	8.03E-04	-2.44E-03	1.70E-01	4.23E-02	2.21E-01	1.98E-01	4.87E-01	4.85E-02	2.26E-01
Eutrfw	kg P-Eq	-3.74E-04	-2.17E-04	-2.15E-04	-3.27E-04	-2.52E-04	-8.37E-04	-2.43E-05	-1.15E-05	-7.70E-05	-1.59E-05	-8.30E-05	-6.69E-05	-1.82E-05	-6.19E-05	-7.82E-05
Eutrm	kg N-Eq	-4.22E+00	-2.96E-01	-3.02E-01	-9.47E-01	-4.57E-01	-2.19E+00	-4.51E-02	-2.13E-02	-6.91E-01	-1.60E+00	-3.84E-01	-3.26E-01	-5.52E-01	-6.79E-01	-2.78E-01
Eutrt	mol N-Eq	-3.98E+00	-2.34E-01	-2.43E-01	-8.49E-01	-3.87E-01	-1.90E+00	-3.56E-02	-1.67E-02	-6.52E-01	-1.55E+00	-3.33E-01	-2.86E-01	-5.22E-01	-5.23E-01	-2.36E-01
HTc	CTUh	-2.36E-01	-6.18E-02	-5.92E-02	-9.81E-02	-7.06E-02	-2.89E-01	-9.45E-03	-4.57E-03	-3.69E-02	-4.87E-02	-5.01E-02	-3.95E-02	-2.94E-02	-1.55E-01	-4.13E-02
HTnc	CTUh	-3.06E+00	-5.63E-01	-5.06E-01	-8.45E-01	-6.00E-01	-3.10E+00	-1.18E-01	-5.84E-02	-3.69E-01	-6.84E-01	-7.40E-01	-5.71E-01	-4.66E-01	-3.17E+00	-5.96E-01
Irhh	kBq U235-Eq	9.03E-04	9.29E-05	2.20E-03	4.72E-05	5.92E-05	-9.05E-05	9.10E-06	1.74E-07	6.10E-04	1.43E-04	4.61E-03	4.33E-03	1.16E-02	6.27E-03	8.46E-03
LU	dimensionless	1.28E-01	1.80E-02	3.29E-02	1.56E-02	1.67E-02	4.05E-03	6.69E-03	9.66E-04	1.07E+00	7.44E-01	9.50E+00	7.61E+00	7.30E-02	3.95E-02	3.68E-02
Teae	kg Sb-Eq	-3.93E-03	-5.23E-04	-4.31E-04	-7.29E-04	-5.07E-04	-3.43E-03	-1.48E-04	-7.42E-05	-3.81E-04	-9.18E-04	-1.02E-03	-7.80E-04	-6.68E-04	-5.04E-03	-8.14E-04
Ozone	kg CFC-11-Eq	-1.94E-10	-1.59E-10	-1.14E-10	-3.32E-10	-2.19E-10	-3.46E-10	-2.47E-11	-1.62E-11	6.23E-10	-7.67E-11	2.19E-11	3.97E-11	2.72E-10	-4.33E-10	-4.94E-12
Pmf	disease incidence	1.49E-09	1.60E-10	2.37E-10	1.32E-10	1.47E-10	4.77E-11	6.26E-11	7.83E-12	2.56E-09	5.52E-10	1.04E-09	8.38E-10	1.01E-09	5.27E-10	2.64E-10
POFhh	kg NMVOC-Eq	9.84E-05	2.22E-05	3.27E-05	1.90E-05	1.98E-05	4.73E-05	4.45E-06	4.05E-07	1.01E-04	2.80E-05	2.15E-04	1.42E-04	7.28E-05	3.95E-05	3.03E-05
WU	m3 world Eq deprived	3.78E-02	3.43E-04	1.51E-03	2.50E-04	2.57E-04	5.45E-04	4.48E-05	7.84E-06	1.53E-01	2.01E-03	2.57E-02	1.78E-02	1.28E-02	6.93E-03	5.06E-03

Figure 30. Summary results of the CFF formula in the CC impact category.

It is remarkable the relevance of the nutrient content factors introduction as a proper correction factor to integrate the compound fertilisers. However, there is an extra factor. The complexity of the product's equivalence definition in the Q_{in}/Q_{out} ratio should be described in the PEFCRs.

As default for alternative fertilising products should be 1, though the nutrient content should be integrated. As a reference, this Q_{in}/Q_{out} ratio is defined in traditional EoL systems in LCA in the system expansion as the substitutability ratio that defines the equivalence between products.

Further specific PEFCR for different alternative fertilising products could be developed. For instance, for compost, ammonium sulphate from manure stripping, etc. This could be developed in each PEFCR, providing the technical parameters for the CFF, basing the discussion on the correct agronomic performance benchmarking.

Another limitation is the definition of the counterparts, which is a central point. In this sense, the selection of the product or products benchmarked as virgins (EV) is difficult due to different motives. The identification of products that could be replaced depends on (i) the location and time constraints, and (ii) the inclusion of transportation and the resolution of the multifunctionality (multiple nutrients) in the mineral compound fertilisers. As an example, Figure 31 presents some variations among the reference products.

Figure 31. Comparative impact of mineral suppliers-products and markets.

Moreover, related to the discussion about the reference product, inherently exist the current consumption patterns per country that differ importantly, depending on the crop types, farmer rents, etc. This aspect plays synergistically with the time horizon and the dynamism of the consumption patterns that can be observed in the extract statistic of IFA database for the case of N (Figure 32)

Figure 32. Consumption patterns and mixes in the EU 27 countries.

5.5. Economic analysis

The aggregated results for the CAPEX and OPEX analysis of the 15 alternative fertilising products can be seen in Table 22. A significant remark is the presence of negative values under the "Other Revenues" category for some products. As explained in Section 3.4, these negative values represent the inclusion of potential revenues, treated as negative costs, in the LCC analysis. Specifically, they refer to companies receiving compensation for using waste as an input material, reflecting a financial gain rather than an expense.

The results in Figure 33 further illustrate the difference between the companies that get revenue for processing waste and those that do not. The first group avoids the financial burden of waste treatment, which in a traditional value chain is carried out by external upstream actors (waste treaters). By valorising waste, these companies reduce their operational costs while also generating income through these avoided expenses typically associated with conventional waste treatment.

This situation highlights the advantage of waste valorisation in industrial processes. Instead of companies paying to get rid of waste, that value shifts to the ones using it to make biofertilisers, showing the economic potential of circular business models, while also sticking to sustainability objectives by reducing waste and increasing resource efficiency.

When looking at the results, we also see that most of the costs are associated with the OPEX, more precisely, the variable costs of OPEX, such as raw materials or energy. This cost distribution could result from the small scale of the companies involved. However, variable operating costs tend to reduce over time when operation grows and become more efficient, with economies of scale achieved, thus it could be expected for these to reduce in the long-term.

The results also suggest that the initial capital investment required to valorise waste into biofertilisers is not a big financial barrier, as CAPEX does not appear as a prominent cost. This opens the door for new players to enter the market, as initial investment does not represent a big entry barrier. This relatively low capital investment can likely be attributed to the low-technological nature of the process of transforming organic waste to biofertilisers, as they mostly rely on standard equipment such as conveyor belts, loaders, tractors and mixers.

Table 22. Results for the CAPEX and OPEX analysis for the 15 products based on 1 kg of product.

	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15
CAPEX	€ 0.0004	€ 0.0004	€ 0.0004	€ 0.0004	€ 0.0004	€ 0.0066	€ 0.0007	€ 0.0007	€ 0.0007	€ 0.0007	€ 0.0130	€ 0.0130	€ 0.0003	€ 0.0003	€ 0.0003
Fixed-Opex	€ 0.0001	€ 0.0001	€ 0.0001	€ 0.0001	€ 0.0001	€ 0.0009	€ 0.0001	€ 0.0001	€ 0.0001	€ 0.0001	€ 0.0023	€ 0.0023	€ 0.0001	€ 0.0001	€ 0.0001
Variable-Opex	€ 0.0371	€ 0.0081	€ 0.0150	€ 0.0066	€ 0.0106	€ 0.0378	€ 0.0091	€ 0.0025	€ 0.0167	€ 0.0453	€ 0.0700	€ 0.0692	€ 0.0428	€ 0.0232	€ 0.0147
Other revenues	-€ 0.0297	-€ 0.0321	-€ 0.0241	-€ 0.0327	-€ 0.0245	€ -	-€ 0.0089	-€ 0.0103	€ -	€ -	€ -	€ -	€ -	€ -	€ -
Net Cost	€ 0.0079	-€ 0.0235	-€ 0.0085	-€ 0.0256	-€ 0.0134	€ 0.0453	€ 0.0011	-€ 0.0069	€ 0.0175	€ 0.0461	€ 0.0853	€ 0.0844	€ 0.0431	€ 0.0236	€ 0.0151

Figure 33. Comparison between the results for the LCC CAPEX-OPEX analysis of the 15 products

5.6. Assessment of the Use on Field of the alternative fertilising products

5.6.1 Environmental assessment of the Use on Field of the alternative fertilising products

The following section presents the results of the environmental assessment of the application of the fifteen BBF across five representative farming systems. The results in Figure 34 show the impact contributions among all environmental impact categories for the specific case study of using P1 in one hectare of horticulture in the EU27. The production of this fertiliser and the required additional synthetic fertilisers are significant contributors across most of the impact categories.

Ammonia (NH_3) and nitrogen oxides (NO_x) emissions to air from fertiliser application also represent the most important drivers in impact categories such as acidification (AC), freshwater ecotoxicity (Etfw), marine and terrestrial eutrophication (Eutrm and Eutrt), Particulate matter formation (Pmf) and Photochemical oxidant formation related to human health (POFhh). Additionally, nitrate ($\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$) runoff in regions where leaching occurs plays a key role in marine eutrophication. Excess of N, including negative effects such as growth of phytoplankton and algal blooms, formation of hypoxic water, increasing the fish kills and decline in health of coral reefs (de Vries, 2021).

Direct and indirect N_2O emissions are the dominant contributors in the climate change impact category. This gas is a greenhouse gas with a global warming potential approximately 273 times that of CO_2 over a 100-year time horizon, according to the Sixth Assessment Report (IPCC, 2021). Both synthetic and alternative fertilising methods drive nitrification and denitrification processes, emitting this GHG into the atmosphere and increasing climate change impacts. Phosphorus emissions are the highest contributing factor for freshwater eutrophication (Eutrfw), since excessive phosphorus enters freshwater bodies via runoff and may contribute to oxygen depletion, pH variability and increases in toxic algal blooms, among others (Jennings et al., 2003).

The impact related to the production of the supplementary synthetic fertiliser to fulfil the NPK requirements (urea, triple superphosphate and potassium chloride) is an important contributor to the majority of other impact categories such as energy resources: non-renewable (ERnr), marine and terrestrial eutrophication, human toxicity, among others, land use, material resources, ozone depletion, particulate matter formation, photochemical oxidant formation and water use. This is due to the material and energy-intensive process of production of the synthetic fertilisers in line with other LCA of fertiliser application.

Figure 34. Impact Contributions of P1 for Horticulture in the EU27

Figure 35 summarises the environmental impact of BBF across all impact categories when fertilising 1 hectare of field crops in the EU27 and compares the normalised impact contributions with the ones related to the production of 1kg of these fertilisers.

The results show that applying only synthetic fertilisers in comparison with using a combination of BBF and synthetic fertilisers results in highest environmental impacts for climate change impact, ozone depletion and materials resources (metals/minerals). However, using exclusively synthetic fertilizers has better impacts than the combination of BBF for the impact categories such as acidification, energy resources, terrestrial and marine eutrophication, human toxicity non-carcinogenic.

When considering the entire *cradle-to-field* life cycle, P9 continues exhibiting the worst environmental performance across most impact categories among the alternative fertilising products, except the climate change category. This is evidence of how decision-making can change and be affected based on the system boundaries and the functional unit, in comparison with studied in the cradle-to-gate perspective in section 5.4. Moreover, the ranking of other fertilisers varies depending on the scope of the assessment, for example, P14, that have a relatively low environmental impact in the climate change impact category when looking solely at production, but it has the highest carbon footprint when assessing it including the application phase.

Impact Contributions for the Fertilisation of Field Crops in EU27 (FU: 1 ha⁻¹ year⁻¹)

Impact Category	Unit	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15	Psynthetic
AC	mol H ⁺ -Eq	5.16E+01	4.88E+01	4.80E+01	4.77E+01	4.77E+01	5.17E+01	5.69E+01	5.80E+01	6.57E+01	6.30E+01	5.41E+01	6.49E+01	6.43E+01	4.96E+01	5.03E+01	4.05E+01
CC	kg CO ₂ -Eq	9.36E+02	1.03E+03	1.07E+03	1.00E+03	1.03E+03	8.65E+02	8.21E+02	8.25E+02	6.57E+02	5.62E+02	1.07E+03	5.70E+02	7.51E+02	1.09E+03	1.01E+03	1.10E+03
ETfw	CTUe	1.21E+03	3.93E+03	4.09E+03	1.74E+03	3.17E+03	2.47E+03	4.61E+03	5.47E+03	3.03E+03	1.94E+03	2.29E+03	3.73E+03	8.05E+03	3.39E+03	1.45E+03	3.93E+03
ERnr	MJ, net calorific value	2.32E+03	1.96E+03	1.96E+03	1.86E+03	1.88E+03	1.98E+03	2.49E+03	2.73E+03	8.78E+03	3.55E+03	2.29E+03	2.42E+03	4.65E+03	2.68E+03	1.87E+03	1.73E+03
Eutrfw	kg P-Eq	2.53E+00	2.50E+00	2.50E+00	2.50E+00	2.50E+00	2.49E+00	2.49E+00	2.49E+00	2.57E+00	2.48E+00	2.56E+00	2.52E+00	2.52E+00	2.54E+00	2.54E+00	2.55E+00
Eutrm	kg N-Eq	1.10E+01	1.09E+01	1.08E+01	1.08E+01	1.08E+01	1.13E+01	1.21E+01	1.23E+01	1.41E+01	1.27E+01	1.13E+01	1.26E+01	1.31E+01	1.09E+01	1.08E+01	6.34E+00
Eutrt	mol N-Eq	2.32E+02	2.28E+02	2.24E+02	2.23E+02	2.23E+02	2.42E+02	2.67E+02	2.72E+02	3.04E+02	2.94E+02	2.42E+02	2.93E+02	2.97E+02	2.22E+02	2.23E+02	1.68E+02
HTc	CTUh	1.33E-06	1.41E-06	1.47E-06	1.23E-06	1.38E-06	1.03E-06	1.45E-06	1.79E-06	1.74E-06	9.88E-07	1.59E-06	9.29E-07	1.68E-06	1.84E-06	1.50E-06	1.80E-06
HTnc	CTUh	7.85E-07	1.27E-06	1.32E-06	1.03E-06	1.06E-06	7.05E-07	2.98E-06	3.65E-06	9.95E-06	1.47E-06	1.47E-06	7.48E-07	4.75E-06	1.41E-06	7.56E-07	6.71E-07
Irhh	kBq U235-Eq	1.10E+00	1.21E+00	1.06E+01	8.79E-01	9.90E-01	5.71E-01	2.32E+00	3.34E+00	6.16E+00	2.47E+00	2.27E+01	7.41E+00	1.31E+02	5.26E+01	1.29E+01	5.00E-01
LU	dimensionless	1.75E+03	1.11E+03	1.19E+03	7.83E+02	1.02E+03	6.72E+02	1.69E+03	2.25E+03	1.03E+04	9.48E+03	4.74E+04	1.43E+04	1.62E+03	1.96E+03	2.10E+03	2.51E+03
OD	kg Sb-Eq	9.71E-06	1.06E-05	1.13E-05	1.03E-05	1.03E-05	8.55E-06	7.12E-06	7.69E-06	2.45E-06	9.47E-06	2.54E-06	6.17E-06	1.25E-05	1.09E-05	1.28E-05	
POFhh	kg CFC-11-Eq	1.42E+01	1.40E+01	1.39E+01	1.36E+01	1.37E+01	1.45E+01	1.64E+01	1.70E+01	1.78E+01	1.72E+01	1.56E+01	1.74E+01	1.81E+01	1.39E+01	1.38E+01	2.60E+00
Pmf	disease incidence	3.09E-04	3.00E-04	2.95E-04	2.91E-04	2.93E-04	3.14E-04	3.52E-04	3.62E-04	4.00E-04	3.83E-04	3.25E-04	3.87E-04	3.89E-04	2.99E-04	3.00E-04	2.75E-04
Teae	kg NMVOC-Eq	2.58E-03	3.02E-03	3.30E-03	2.67E-03	2.97E-03	2.07E-03	1.90E-03	1.96E-03	2.16E-03	6.40E-04	2.42E-03	1.08E-03	2.02E-03	3.32E-03	2.85E-03	3.61E-03
WU	m3 world Eq deprived	6.09E+02	5.72E+02	6.12E+02	5.98E+02	6.09E+02	4.36E+02	2.60E+02	2.29E+02	1.39E+03	4.88E+01	6.53E+02	1.36E+02	1.70E+02	7.27E+02	6.90E+02	7.74E+02

Normalized Impact Contributions (FU: 1 ha⁻¹ year⁻¹)

Impact Category	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15
AC	0.79	0.74	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.79	0.87	0.88	1.00	0.96	0.82	0.99	0.98	0.75	0.77
CC	0.86	0.95	0.98	0.91	0.94	0.79	0.75	0.75	0.60	0.51	0.98	0.52	0.69	1.00	0.92
ETfw	0.15	0.49	0.51	0.22	0.39	0.31	0.57	0.68	0.38	0.24	0.28	0.46	1.00	0.42	0.18
ERnr	0.26	0.22	0.22	0.21	0.21	0.23	0.28	0.31	1.00	0.40	0.26	0.28	0.53	0.31	0.21
Eutrfw	0.98	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97	1.00	0.97	1.00	0.98	0.98	0.99	0.99
Eutrm	0.78	0.77	0.77	0.76	0.76	0.80	0.85	0.87	1.00	0.90	0.80	0.90	0.93	0.77	0.76
Eutrt	0.76	0.75	0.74	0.73	0.73	0.80	0.88	0.89	1.00	0.97	0.79	0.96	0.98	0.73	0.73
HTc	0.72	0.76	0.80	0.67	0.75	0.56	0.79	0.97	0.95	0.54	0.87	0.50	0.91	1.00	0.82
HTnc	0.08	0.13	0.13	0.10	0.11	0.07	0.30	0.37	1.00	0.15	0.15	0.08	0.48	0.14	0.08
Irhh	0.01	0.01	0.08	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.02	0.17	0.06	1.00	0.40	0.10
LU	0.04	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.04	0.05	0.22	0.20	1.00	0.30	0.03	0.04	0.04
Teae	0.78	0.85	0.90	0.82	0.87	0.69	0.57	0.62	0.64	0.20	0.76	0.20	0.50	1.00	0.88
OD	0.78	0.77	0.76	0.75	0.76	0.80	0.91	0.94	0.98	0.95	0.86	0.96	1.00	0.77	0.76
Pmf	0.77	0.75	0.74	0.73	0.73	0.79	0.88	0.91	1.00	0.96	0.81	0.97	0.97	0.75	0.75
POFhh	0.78	0.91	0.99	0.81	0.89	0.62	0.57	0.59	0.65	0.19	0.73	0.32	0.61	1.00	0.86
WU	0.44	0.41	0.44	0.43	0.44	0.31	0.19	0.16	1.00	0.04	0.47	0.10	0.12	0.52	0.50

Normalized Impact Contributions (FU: Production of 1kg BBF)

Impact category	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15
AC	0.31	0.05	0.09	0.04	0.05	0.09	0.01	0.00	1.00	0.11	0.27	0.22	0.41	0.22	0.12
CC	0.66	0.36	0.41	0.25	0.25	0.70	0.03	0.00	0.49	0.18	1.00	0.66	0.52	0.28	0.22
ETfw	0.98	0.03	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.14	0.10	0.08	0.27	0.15	0.07
ERnr	0.86	0.15	0.26	0.10	0.11	0.80	0.02	0.00	0.37	0.18	0.53	0.46	1.00	0.54	0.52
Eutrfw	0.35	0.04	0.08	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.07	0.55	0.46	0.35	0.19	0.12
Eutrm	0.13	0.02	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.01	0.00	1.00	0.06	0.15	0.12	0.23	0.12	0.07
Eutrt	0.22	0.03	0.06	0.03	0.03	0.06	0.01	0.00	1.00	0.09	0.20	0.16	0.20	0.11	0.07
HTc	0.79	0.11	0.15	0.08	0.08	0.24	0.03	0.01	1.00	0.32	0.51	0.44	0.71	0.38	0.23
HTnc	0.23	0.04	0.07	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.00	1.00	0.06	0.16	0.12	0.15	0.08	0.06
Irhh	0.08	0.01	0.19	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.01	0.40	0.37	1.00	0.54	0.73
LU	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.11	0.08	1.00	0.80	0.01	0.00	0.00
Teae	1.00	0.16	0.31	0.11	0.11	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.75	0.10	0.16	0.14	0.48	0.26	0.15
OD	0.94	0.11	0.15	0.08	0.08	1.00	0.02	0.00	0.94	0.15	0.28	0.24	0.48	0.26	0.20
Pmf	0.60	0.07	0.10	0.06	0.06	0.04	0.03	0.00	1.00	0.22	0.41	0.33	0.39	0.21	0.11
POFhh	0.46	0.10	0.15	0.09	0.09	0.22	0.02	0.00	0.47	0.13	1.00	0.66	0.34	0.18	0.14
WU	0.25	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.01	0.17	0.12	0.08	0.05	0.03

Figure 35. Impact Contributions for the Fertilisation of Field crops in the EU27 (FU: 1 ha⁻¹ year⁻¹) compared to the Impact Contributions (FU: Production of 1kg BBF)

These outcomes show the importance of the scope and functional unit that is chosen for the environmental assessment of the alternative fertilising products. The assessment limited to the production phase can underestimate their true footprint. The fertiliser’s efficiency to fulfil the agronomic needs and its related application emissions will significantly affect the overall impacts.

Furthermore, as the NPK requirements differ by crop type (Table 5), the analysis in Figure 36 further explores the impact category Climate Change on the fifteen BBF when applied in five different farming systems in EU27, compared to the use of synthetic fertilisers alone. The results show that even though the climate impact varies depending on the farming system according to the amount of NPK required, there are no significant differences in the ranking of BBFs regarding their carbon footprint across types of farming. However, the total environmental impact does differ among farming types because it is correlated with the amount of NPK required. Horticulture, which has the highest NPK demand per hectare, shows the largest footprint and other grazing livestock, which has the lowest NPK requirement, has the smallest footprint.

Figure 36. Climate Change Impact per BFF in EU27 by Farming Type

5.6.2. Sensitivity analysis of the environmental assessment of the Use on Field of the alternative fertilising products

To validate the methodology for assessing the application phase of alternative fertilising products, the following sensitivity analyses are performed to assess the change in overall results related to:

Regional Variability

The emission factors used (IPCC, 2019, as cited in Novafert, 2024) to calculate direct and indirect emissions vary between dry and wet climates. Country-specific data for Finland and Spain are used instead of the baseline to explore the impact of regional differences on the results. For the selection of emission factors for direct, indirect and leaching N₂O emissions, Finland is considered a wet climate and Spain a dry climate (Table 23).

Table 23. Comparison of the NPK recommendations for field crops in EU27, Spain and Finland from FADN (2024) (EU Commission, n.d.-b)

Country	Crop	N (kg/ha)	P ₂ O ₅ (kg/ha)	K ₂ O (kg/ha)
EU27	Field crops	84.50	24.57	27.56
Spain		59.73	36.03	27.01
Finland		62.49	14.72	17.80

Figure 37 shows the climate change impact per fertiliser per country for field crops. There are no significant changes in the ranking of fertilisers between the outcomes for EU27 and Finland, only a lower overall CC impact due to a lower NPK requirement. This can be explained because for the baseline assessment, EU27 was considered as a wet climate, as well as Finland, so there are no changes in the selection of emission factors for direct, indirect and leaching N₂O emissions (IPCC, 2019, as cited in Novafert, 2024).

However, for the assessment of Spain, the emission factors for dry climate are used (IPCC, 2019). These emission factors are smaller for dry climates; there are no differences in the emission factor for direct N₂O emissions between synthetic fertiliser and BBF, and it is assumed that there are no leaching emissions. As a result, for the case of Spain, not all the BBFs have a smaller climate change impact than synthetic fertilisers. The reduced contribution of direct and indirect N₂O emissions means that other factors, such as production, fertilising method and transport, become more significant, changing the ranking of the fertilisers.

This sensitivity analysis shows that the environmental performance of fertilisers varies depending on the climatic conditions of the field where these are applied. It emphasises the need for a regional assessment to calculate the impacts accurately.

Figure 37. Sensitivity Analysis for Regional Variability for Climate Change Impact

Influence of the emissions of heavy metals

The following analysis provides an environmental assessment of the use in the field of P6, considering its heavy metals content (Table 24. Heavy Metals Content of P6), which is the only alternative fertilising product for which detailed data on these concentrations were available.

Table 24. Heavy Metals Content of P6

Heavy Metals	Lead (Pb)	Cadmium (Cd)	Chromium (Cr)	Copper (Cu)	Iron (Fe)	Mercury (Hg)	Nickel (Ni)	Zinc (Zn)
Content (mg/kg P6)	0.9	1	30	341.5	2701.5	0.64	16	1137.35

When including the heavy metals emissions in the environmental assessment of fertilising one hectare of field crops, they play a key role in the impact categories of human toxicity (carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic) and freshwater ecotoxicity (Figure 39).

Figure 38. Impact Contributions P6 with heavy metals emissions

Figure 40 further explores the specific contribution of each heavy metal to the impact categories affected. Mercury (Hg), even being in a lower quantity than the other heavy metals, has the highest impact in both Human toxicity carcinogenic (HTc) and non-carcinogenic (HTnc) with values of 5.6×10^{-7} and 6.6×10^{-5} CTUh (Comparative Toxic Unit for humans) respectively. Iron (Fe) has the highest impact in freshwater ecotoxicity (ETfw) with 739.38 CTUe (Comparative Toxic Unit for freshwater ecosystems). Other metals like Zinc (Zn) and Nickel (Ni) also have a significant influence on these impact categories.

To sum up, heavy metals affect the impact categories of human toxicity and freshwater ecotoxicity, with mercury demonstrating the most critical risk to human health and iron to freshwater ecosystems. This sensitivity analysis shows that to give a comprehensive assessment of the overall impacts of human toxicity and freshwater ecotoxicity, it is important to consider the heavy metal content of the fertilisers together with the impacts of producing synthetic fertilisers and ammonia emissions.

Figure 39. Impact Contributions of Heavy Metals for P6

5.6.3. Economic analysis of the Use on Field of the alternative fertilising products

An economic analysis of the application of the alternative fertilising products is developed to assess their profitability and to identify the main factors influencing the overall cost of fertilisation. Since there is insufficient primary data on the market price for these fertilisers, their price has instead been estimated as the break-even price at which fertilisation with alternative fertilising products would be economically competitive with the baseline scenario of using only synthetic fertilisers. **Error! No s'ha trobat l'origen de la referència.** shows the contribution of each cost source to the total cost of fertilising one hectare, assuming the overall cost equals that of the synthetic fertiliser baseline. The outcomes show that production costs of both BBF and synthetic fertilisers are the most dominant contributors to total cost, while transport or fertilising method contribute comparatively little for all farming types.

Figure 40 Economic Analysis of the Use on Field of Fertilisers with an estimated competitive price for BBF

The analysis in Figure 41 examines the profitability of the alternative fertilising products according to the estimated cost-competitive price for EU27 and field crops (estimated price for other farming types can be found in Annexes III Table 25). P1 and P6 result to be the most profitable options, both performing well due to their nutrient efficiency (Table 16), combined with low production costs. Contrarily, P11, P10 and P13 show a negative profit, making them economically unfeasible options. P11 has the highest production cost and does not have a very rich NPK profile, resulting in the lowest profit of all fertilisers analysed.

P7 and P8, despite having low nutrient content and, therefore, requiring the highest quantities to meet fertilisation requirements, remain on the profitable side. These fertilisers have very low production costs as they receive revenue for the treatment of the main raw material. Similarly, P4 has the lowest production costs, but this factor alone does not translate into the highest profit. However, its profit is still relatively high compared to most of the other options.

Figure 41. Production Cost, Estimated Price and Profit for BBF

To sum up, the most profitable fertilisers have a balance between nutrient quality and cost-efficient production. These fertilisers could have a lower price than synthetic fertilisers (due to market conditions, EU policy instruments or reducing profitability) to further improve the competitiveness and promote their use.

Additionally, transport and fertilising methods do not have a significant contribution to the total cost of fertilisation, though they can be a technical issue. Therefore, if alternative fertilising products benefit from secondary revenues from waste treatment, it will provide an advantage to nutrient-poor but cost-efficient products. However, revenues should be higher, so they are more profitable than other products that have a better NPK profile.

6. Conclusions

The present deliverable evaluates the environmental performance of thirteen products and value chains from five European companies with the PEF-wise method developed in the NOVAFERT project.

The assessment had a double aim: on one side, the assessment of the alternative fertilising products and the comparison with their mineral counterparts, and secondly, to validate and test the different methodological choices of the PEF-wise method and other LCA choices such as the Functional unit, the allocation procedure, the system boundaries or the CFF.

In a *cradle-to-gate* perspective, all products had a lower environmental footprint than their mineral counterparts, even if for each product and impact category, the drivers differ significantly. The main hotspots identified across fertilisers are the use of chemical products (such as lime and sulfuric acid), energy consumption (including both environmental impacts of the production of energy sources and the emissions from fossil fuel combustion) and the addition of nutrient sources (whether mineral or organic).

The low impact in all the categories is remarkable, but specifically, the low contribution in the climate change category. This evidence highlights the synergies between nutrient recycling and the decarbonization of agricultural systems and the food sector. However, one limitation of the present study and methodology is the exclusion of other non-LCA impacts and benefits that most of the products assessed herein can provide, such as organic carbon sources for soil health.

The deliverable has assessed important methodological choices such as the use of different Functional units and their effect on the decision-making process. The results are that the use of complementary FUs is valuable to enrich the decision-making process. Nonetheless, further investigations could look for other Functional Units based on the plant available nutrients or other scoring systems such as the mineral fertiliser index.

In relation to the allocation system, the use of economic allocation seems the default system for the resolution of multifunctionality in the processes and a fair split of environmental responsibility. However, this is sensitive to price changes and market volatility.

The present study overcomes the adaptation of CFF to the case of nutrient recycling systems and alternative fertilising products. This allowed the proper and robust comparison with mineral fertilisers, being all the alternative fertilising products lower impact than their mineral counterparts under the study conditions. Nonetheless, there are still some methodological questions that provide uncertainty, such as the choice of mineral counterparts.

Moreover, the CFF study allowed a pertinent discussion about the responsibility splitting between the generators of the wastes/secondary nutrient sources and the application/end-user of the fertilising product. The result is a benefit to the nutrient recyclers but a low benefit to the end-users. This effect could hinder the adoption of thinking in the decarbonization as a driver in decision-making.

The economic analysis highlighted the cost-effectiveness of the nutrient recycling processes. Moreover, the nutrient recovery from different waste treatments includes an income because of the waste treatment, which in most cases can significantly affect the financial sustainability of the activities, favouring the nutrient recycling.

The analysis, *cradle-to-gate*, was complemented with a *cradle-to-field* assessment for the inclusion of the use/application phase. For that, 6 different crop fertilisation demands in two climatic conditions of Europe were studied to be fulfilled with the 15 BBFs and complemented with mineral counterparts. This extended the assessment including the direct and indirect emissions from fertiliser application, which has had a key role in the overall environmental impact of both synthetic and BBF. The ranking with the *cradle-to-field* perspective differs from the *cradle-to-gate* perspective. That reinforces the idea that the PEF-wise method for BBFs and fertilising products, in general, cannot be provided just based on the mass of BBFs or the nutrient content.

However, the variability in the results among crops and regional climate conditions highlighted the importance of doing an assessment that considers regional climate and agronomic characteristics of different types of farming, as the impacts vary significantly depending on these factors. Additionally, the economic analysis questioned the economic feasibility of some alternative fertilisers, especially those with low nutrient content and high production costs.

Moreover, the deliverable summarises an important number of inventories with high-quality data in most of the flows. E.g. Electricity use, chemical consumption, etc. However, the use of emission factors in certain processes was needed to estimate mainly the direct and indirect N emissions (NH_3 and N_2O) with their respective effect on the Climate Change category, among others. These inventories will conform the Deliverable 2.4 in ILCD-compliant format.

The document may support further developments and implementation of the PEF initiative, as well as other recycling activities ruled by the CFF, such as recycling systems or carbon capture for utilisation technologies. The present opened a debate about how the current normative framework of PEF distributes the responsibility to recyclers and consumers of recycled products.

Furthermore, other policy and regulatory decisions could be improved by more robust evaluations and comments that could enrich the LCA support results. Particularly, favouring the adoption of the foremost environmentally friendly alternative fertilising products.

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Annex I. Life Cycle Inventories

LCIs from fertilisers produced by Company A

Table A1. Life Cycle Inventory for Product 1.

Process level 1	Process level 2	Flow	Amount per 1kg P1	Units	I/O
P1 Production	P1 Production	P1 (liquid fertilizer)	1.00E+00	kg	O
P1 Production	Quicklime Receipt	Quicklime production	1.68E-02	kg	I
P1 Production	Quicklime Receipt	Quicklime transport	9.93E-03	tkm	I
P1 Production	Biodegradable waste reception	Biodegradable waste	8.74E-01	kg	I
P1 Production	Biodegradable waste reception	Biodegradable waste transport	2.34E-06	tkm	I
P1 Production	P1 Production	Urea	4.63E-02	kg	I
P1 Production	P1 Production	KCL	6.29E-02	kg	I
P1 Production	Electricity for Plant Operation	Electricity from grid	4.05E-04	kWh	I
P1 Production	Water for Plant Operation	Water for plant operation (Tap water)	2.16E-07	m3	I
P1 Production	Dosing & mixing	Fuel (Diesel)	3.09E-04	L	I
P1 Production	Dosing & mixing	CO2 emissions from diesel combustion	8.20E-01	g	O
P1 Production	Dosing & mixing	CH4 emissions from diesel combustion	1.11E-04	g	O
P1 Production	Dosing & mixing	N2O from diesel combustion	6.65E-06	g	O
P1 Production	Dosing & mixing	N2O emissions (lime application)	1.50E-01	g	O
P1 Production	Dosing & mixing	NH3 emissions (lime application)	1.48E+01	g	O

Table A2. Life Cycle Inventory for Product 2.

Process level 1	Process level 2	Flow	Amount per 1kg P2	Units	I/O
P2 Production	P2	P2 Production	1.00E+00	kg	O
P2 Production	Quicklime Receipt	Quicklime Production	5.66E-02	kg	I
P2 Production	Quicklime Receipt	Quicklime Transport	3.34E-02	tkm	I
P2 Production	Biodegradable waste Receipt	Biodegradable waste	9.43E-01	kg	I
P2 Production	Biodegradable waste Receipt	Biodegradable waste Transport	2.53E-06	tkm	I
P2 Production	Electricity for Plant Operation	Electricity from grid	4.38E-04	kWh	I
P2 Production	Water for Plant Operation	Water for plant operation (Tap water)	2.33E-07	m3	I
P2 Production	Dosing & mixing	Fuel (Diesel)	3.34E-04	L	I
P2 Production	Dosing & mixing	CO2 emissions from diesel combustion	8.85E-01	g	O
P2 Production	Dosing & mixing	CH4 emissions from diesel combustion	1.20E-04	g	O
P2 Production	Dosing & mixing	N2O from diesel combustion	7.17E-06	g	O
P2 Production	Dosing & mixing	N2O emissions (lime application)	1.68E-02	g	O
P2 Production	Dosing & mixing	NH3 emissions (lime application)	1.66E+00	g	O

Table A3. Life Cycle Inventory for Product 3.

Process level 1	Process level 2	Flow	Amount per 1kg P3	Units	I/O
P3 Production	P3 Production	P3	1.00E+00	kg	O
P3 Production	Quicklime reception	Quicklime Production	5.66E-02	kg	O
P3 Production	Quicklime reception	Quicklime Transport	3.34E-02	tkm	I
P3 Production	Compost Reception	Compost	2.36E-01	kg	I
P3 Production	Compost Reception	Compost Transport	3.74E-08	tkm	I
P3 Production	Biodegradable waste Reception	Biodegradable waste	7.08E-01	kg	I
P3 Production	Biodegradable waste Reception	Biodegradable waste Transport	1.89E-06	tkm	I
P3 Production	Plant operation	Electricity from grid	4.38E-04	kWh	I
P3 Production	Plant operation	Water for plant operation	2.33E-07	m3	I
P3 Production	Dosing & mixing	Fuel (Diesel)	3.34E-04	L	I
P3 Production	Dosing & mixing	CO2 emissions from diesel combustion	8.85E-01	g	O
P3 Production	Dosing & mixing	CH4 emissions from diesel combustion	1.20E-04	g	O
P3 Production	Dosing & mixing	N2O from diesel combustion	7.17E-06	g	O
P3 Production	Dosing & mixing	N2O emissions (lime application)	1.15E-02	g	O
P3 Production	Dosing & mixing	NH3 emissions (lime application)	1.14E+00	g	O

Table A4. Life Cycle Inventory for Product 4.

Process level 1	Process level 2	Flow	Amount per 1kg P4	Units	I/O
P4 Production	P4 Production	P4 (solid fertilizer with ash incorporation)	1.00E+00	kg	O
P4 Production	Quicklime Receipt	Quicklime Production	3.85E-02	kg	I
P4 Production	Quicklime Receipt	Quicklime Transport	2.27E-02	tkm	I
P4 Production	Biodegradable waste Receipt	Biodegradable waste	9.62E-01	kg	I
P4 Production	Biodegradable waste Receipt	Biodegradable waste Transport	2.83E-06	tkm	I
P4 Production	Ash Receipt	Ash	9.62E-02	kg	I
P4 Production	Ash Receipt	Ash Transport	1.00E-02	tkm	I
P4 Production	Plant operation	Electricity from grid	4.91E-04	kWh	I
P4 Production	Plant operation	Water for plant operation	2.61E-07	m3	I
P4 Production	Dosing & mixing	Fuel (Diesel)	3.74E-04	L	I
P4 Production	Dosing & mixing	CO2 emissions from diesel combustion	9.92E-01	g	O
P4 Production	Dosing & mixing	CH4 emissions from diesel combustion	1.35E-04	g	O
P4 Production	Dosing & mixing	N2O from diesel combustion	8.04E-06	g	O
P4 Production	Dosing & mixing	N2O emissions (lime application)	1.71E-02	g	O
P4 Production	Dosing & mixing	NH3 emissions (lime application)	1.69E+00	g	O

Table A5. Life Cycle Inventory for Product 5.

Process level 1	Process level 2	Flow	Amount per 1kg P5	Unit	I/O
P5 Production	P5 Production	P5 Production (solid fertilizer with compos and ash)	1.00E+00	kg	O
P5 Production	Quicklime Receipt	Quicklime Production	3.85E-02	kg	O
P5 Production	Quicklime Receipt	Quicklime Transport	2.27E-02	tkm	I
P5 Production	Compost Receipt	Compost	1.44E-01	kg	I
P5 Production	Compost Receipt	Compost Transport	3.43E-08	tkm	I
P5 Production	Biodegradable waste Receipt	Biodegradable waste	7.21E-01	kg	I
P5 Production	Biodegradable waste Receipt	Biodegradable waste Transport	1.93E-06	tkm	I
P5 Production	Ash Receipt	Ash	9.62E-02	kg	I
P5 Production	Ash Receipt	Ash Transport	1.00E-02	tkm	I
P5 Production	Plant operation	Electricity from grid	4.46E-04	kWh	I
P5 Production	Plant operation	Water for plant operation	2.37E-07	m3	I
P5 Production	Dosing & Mixing	Fuel (Diesel)	3.40E-04	L	I
P5 Production	Dosing & Mixing	CO2 emissions from diesel combustion	9.02E-01	g	O
P5 Production	Dosing & Mixing	CH4 emissions from diesel combustion	1.22E-04	g	O
P5 Production	Dosing & Mixing	N2O from diesel combustion	7.31E-06	g	O
P5 Production	Dosing & Mixing	N2O emissions (lime application)	1.28E-02	g	O
P5 Production	Dosing & Mixing	NH3 emissions (lime application)	1.27E+00	g	O

LCIs from fertilisers produced by Company B

Table A6. Life Cycle Inventory for Product 6.

Process level 1	Process level 2	Flow	Annual total amount	Units	I/O	Reference flow
Treatment pig slurry	Pig slurry Receipt	Pig slurry	6.55E+04	t	I	r
Treatment pig slurry	Pig slurry Receipt	Pig slurry transport	3.80E+05	tkm	I	
Treatment pig slurry	Sulphuric acid Receipt	Sulphuric acid (H ₂ SO ₄)	6.86E+02	t	I	
Treatment pig slurry	Plant operation	Electricity from the grid	3.85E+06	kWhe	I	
Treatment pig slurry	Plant operation	Water	5.28E+04	m ³	I	
Treatment pig slurry	Heat and electricity Cogeneration	Natural gas injection	2.34E+07	m ³	I	
Treatment pig slurry	Heat and electricity Cogeneration	Produced Electricity supplied to the grid	9.80E+07	kWhe	O	
Treatment pig slurry	Plant operation	NOx Emissions	4.74E+09	mg	O	
Treatment pig slurry	Plant operation	SO ₂ Emissions	4.22E+08	mg	O	
Treatment pig slurry	Plant operation	Formaldehyd Emissions	8.33E+07	mg	O	
Treatment pig slurry	Plant operation	CO ₂ Emissions (biogenic)	2.07E+08	g	O	
Treatment pig slurry	Plant operation	CH ₄ Emissions	1.51E+08	g	O	
Treatment pig slurry	Plant operation	CO ₂ Emissions (combustion natural gas)	5.05E+10	g	O	
Treatment pig slurry	Plant operation	Water Emissions	6.23E+04	t	O	
Treatment pig slurry	P6 Production	P6	2.96E+03	t	O	

LCIs from fertilisers produced by Company C

Table A7. Life Cycle Inventory for Product 7.

Process level 1	Process level 2	Flow	Amount per 1kg P7	Units	I/O	Reference flow
P7 Production	P7 Production	P7	1.00E+00	kg	O	r
P7 Production	Primary sludge Receipt	Primary sludge	1.95E-03	kg	I	
P7 Production	Primary sludge Receipt	Transport of primary sludge	5.27E-04	tkm	I	
P7 Production	Mixed sludge Receipt	Mixed sludge	8.58E-01	kg	I	
P7 Production	Mixed sludge Receipt	Transport of mixed sludge	1.72E-04	tkm	I	
P7 Production	Peat Receipt	Peat	3.38E-02	kg	I	
P7 Production	Slack lime Receipt	Slaked lime	6.32E-02	kg	I	
P7 Production	Slack lime Receipt	Transport of slaked lime to processing	1.87E-02	tkm	I	
P7 Production	Processing	Processing by wheelloader, fuel consumption	5.70E-04	L	I	
P7 Production	Processing	CO2 emissions light fuel oil	1.58E+00	g	O	
P7 Production	Processing	CH4 emissions light fuel oil	2.11E-04	g	O	
P7 Production	Processing	N2O emissions light fuel oil	1.28E-05	g	O	
P7 Production	Processing	N2O emissions (lime application)	1.48E-10	g	O	
P7 Production	Processing	NH3 emissions (lime application)	1.46E-08	g	O	
P7 Production	Transport	Product delivery to end users	8.10E-02	tkm	I	
Production of slacked lime	Processing	Slaked lime	6.32E-02	kg	O	r
Production of slacked lime	Burnt lime Receipt	Burnt lime	5.38E-02	kg	I	
Production of slacked lime	Burnt lime Receipt	Transport of burnt lime to processing (water addition)	1.01E-03	tkm	I	
Production of slacked lime	Processing	Water (tap water)	9.49E-03	kg	I	
Production of slacked lime	Processing	Processing by wheelloader, fuel consumption (light fuel oil)	7.00E-04	L	I	
Production of slacked lime	Processing	CO2 emissions light fuel oil	1.93E+00	g	O	
Production of slacked lime	Processing	CH4 emissions light fuel oil	2.59E-04	g	O	
Production of slacked lime	Processing	N2O emissions light fuel oil	1.57E-05	g	O	

Table A8. Life Cycle Inventory for Product 8.

Process level 1	Process level 2	Flow	Amount per 1kg P8	Units	I/O
P8 Production	P8 Production	P8	1.00E+00	kg	O
P8 Production	Mixed sludge Receipt	Mixed sludge	1.00E+00	kg	I
P8 Production	Primary sludge Receipt	Mixed sludge Transport from mill to processing	3.00E-03	tkm	I
P8 Production	Primary sludge Receipt	Processing by wheelloader, fuel consumption (light fuel)	1.00E-04	L	I
P8 Production	P8 Production	CO2 emissions light fuel oil	2.76E-01	g	O
P8 Production	P8 Production	CH4 emissions light fuel oil	3.70E-05	g	O
P8 Production	P8 Production	N2O emissions light fuel oil	2.24E-06	g	O
P8 Production	P8 Production	N2O emissions (lime application)	8.36E-10	g	O
P8 Production	P8 Production	NH3 emissions (lime application)	8.28E-08	g	O

Table A9. Life Cycle Inventory for Product 9.

Process level 1	Process level 2	Flow	Amount for 1 kg P9	Units	I/O
P9 production	P9 production	P9		1 kg	O
P9 production	P9 production	Concentrated potato cell sap transport to intermediate storage	0.0035	tkm	I
P9 production	P9 production	Concentrated potato cell sap (economic allocation considering potato starch)	0.056678557	kg	I

Table A10. Life Cycle Inventory for Product 10.

Process level 1	Process level 2	Flow	Amount for 1 kg P10	Units	I/O
P10 production	P10 production	P10		1 kg	O
P10 production	P10 production	Vinasse transport by truck	0.1415	tkm	I
P10 production	P10 production	Vinasse transport by ship	0.0865	tkm	I
P10 production	P10 production	Vinasse from yeast production (economic allocation from fooder yeast)	0.003332505	kg	I

LCIs from fertilisers produced by Company D

Table A11. Life Cycle Inventory for Products 11 and 12.

COMMON PROCESSES FOR P11 AND P12					
Process level 1	Process level 2	Flow	Amount per 1t Dried Compost	Units	I/O
Pre-treatment_Farm Level	Pre-treatment_Farm Level	Mix of cow manure and sawdust	2.719431761	t	O
Pre-treatment_Farm Level	Pre-treatment_Farm level	Cow manure	1.391079747	t	I
Pre-treatment_Farm Level	Pre-treatment_Farm level	Sawdust	1.328352013	t	I
Composting	Composting	Mature Compost	2.34075919	t	O
Compost	Composting	Mix of cow manure and sawdust	2.719431761	t	I
Compost	Composting	Bark structuring agent	0.419768461	t	I
Compost	Composting	Fuel (Diesel) for composting	0.664176007	L	I
Compost	Composting	Emissions CO2 from Diesel Combustion	1.777334994	kg CO2	O
Compost	Composting	Emissions CH4 from Diesel Combustion	0.0002399	kg CH4	O
Compost	Composting	Emissions N2O from Diesel Combustion	0.0002399	Kg N2O	O
Compost	Composting	Electricity for composting	0.288552189	kwh	I
Compost	Composting	Water	0.66463724	m3	O
Compost	Composting	(Direct) Emissions N2O	3.54227E-07	t	O
Compost	Composting	(Indirect) Emissions NH3	2.03865E-06	t	O
Compost Sieving	Compost Sieving	Sieved compost	1.713020617	t	O
Compost Sieving	Compost Sieving	Mature Compost	2.34075919	t	I
Compost Sieving	Compost Sieving	Electricity for sieving	0.285540335	kwh	I
Compost Sieving	Compost Sieving	Rest Compost Sieving	1.087495964	t	O
Compost Drying	Driying	Dried compost (20% humidity)	1	t	O
Compost Drying	Driying	Sieved compost	1.713020617	t	I
Compost Drying	Driying	Electricity for Drying	4.427840044	kwh	I
Compost Drying	Driying	Water Evaporation	0.95682856	t	O
SPECIFIC PROCESSES FOR P11					
Process level 1	Process level 2	Flow	Amount per 1t fertilizer P11	Units	I/O
Mixing Compost + Apple Biochar	Mixing	Mixed Output (P11)	1	t	O
Mixing Compost + Apple Biochar	Mixing	Dried compost (20% humidity)	0.901496881	t	I
Mixing Compost + Apple Biochar	Mixing	Apple biochar	0.098128898	t	I
Mixing Compost + Apple Biochar	Mixing	Electricity Mixing	8.06877921	kwh	I
Pelletization P11	Pelletization	Pelletized P11	1	t	O
Pelletization P11	Pelletization	Mixed Output P11	1	t	I
Pelletization P11	Pelletization	Electricity Pelletization	37	kwh	I
SPECIFIC PROCESSES FOR P12					
Process level 1	Process level 2	Flow	Amount per 1t fertilizer P12	Units	I/O
Mixing Compost + Vinyard Biochar	Mixing	Mixed Output (P12)	1	T	O
Mixing Compost + Vinyard Biochar	Mixing	Dried compost (20% humidity)	1.050677152	t	I
Mixing Compost + Vinyard Biochar	Mixing	Vinyard biochar	0.053058104	t	I
Mixing Compost + Vinyard Biochar	Mixing	Electricity Mixing	4.096085627	kwh	I
Pelletized P12	Pelletization	Pelletized P12	1	t	O
Pelletized P12	Pelletization	Mixed Output P12	1	t	I
Pelletized P12	Pelletization	Electricity Pelletization	37	kwh	I

LCIs from fertilisers produced by Company E

Table A12. Life Cycle Inventory for Products 13, 14 and 15.

SEPARATION LIQUID - SOLID					
Process Level 1	Process Level 2	Flow	Amount per 1kg digestate	Unit	I/O
Digestion	Anaerobic Digestion	Digestate		1 kg	O
Separation	Separation	Digestate		1 kg	I
		Electricity		0.008 Kwh/kg	I
		Polymer		0.000658571 Kg/Kg dig	I
	Separation	Solid Fraction		0.161856906 Kg/Kg dig	O
	Separation	Liquid Fraction		0.838143094 Kg/Kg dig	O
LIQUID FRACTION (P.13+P14)					
Process Level 1	Process Level 2	Flow	Amount per 1kg digestate	Unit	I/O
Liquid Fraction	Flotation	Liquid Fraction		0.838143094 Kg/Kg dig	I
		Electricity Flotation		0.0000876 Kwh/kg	I
		Floating solid fraction		0.024294671 Kg/Kg dig	O
	Ultrafiltration	Liquid Fraction		0.813018624 Kg/Kg dig	I
		Electricity Ultrafiltration		0.00006875 Kwh/kg	I
		Liquid Fraction Rejection		0.162594505 Kg/Kg dig	O
	reverse osmosis	Liquid Fraction		0.650424119 Kg/Kg dig	I
		Electricity Reverse Osmosis		5.41674E-05 Kwh/kg	I
		Permeate		0.528443666 Kg/Kg dig	O
		Rejection		0.121934354 Kg/Kg dig	O
	Evaporator	Reverse Osmosis Rejection		0.121934354 Kg/Kg dig	I
		Electricity Evaporator		0.001536373 Kwh/kg	I
		Ultrafiltrate rejection		0.162594505 Kg/Kg dig	I
		Sulfuric Acid		0.000487737 Kg/Kg dig	I
		Concentrate Fertilizer (P13)		0.024386871 Kg/Kg dig	O
		Ammonium sulfate (P14)		0.001219344 Kg/Kg dig	O
		Distilled Water		0.097547483 Kg/Kg dig	O
SOLID FRACTION (P15)					
Process Level 1	Process Level 2	Flow	Amount per 1kg digestate	Unit	I/O
Solid Fraction	Bio-drying	Solid Fraction		0.161856906 Kg/Kg dig	I
		Electricity Biodrying		0.004043007 Kwh/kg	I
		Evaporated Solid Fraction		0.121426837 Kg/Kg dig	O
		NH3		0.000476582 Kg/Kg dig	O
	Pelletizing	Dried Solid Fraction		0.040430068 Kg/Kg dig	I
		Electricity		0.001495913 Kwh/kg	I
		Pelletized Product (P15)		0.040430068 Kg/Kg dig	O

Annex II. Impact results of the LCA for FU: mass of nutrient content (N, P₂O and K₂O) of the fertiliser

Table A13. Impact contribution results of the LCA for the 15 products (Functional Unit: 1 kg of N)

Impact category	Unit	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15
AC	mol H+-Eq	3.32E-03	5.49E-03	1.38E-02	4.61E-03	6.36E-03	1.13E-03	2.55E-03	4.19E-04	1.64E-01	5.29E-03	9.33E-03	9.93E-03	2.26E-02	1.39E-03	5.26E-03
CC	kg CO ₂ -Eq	8.83E-01	4.64E+00	7.55E+00	3.23E+00	4.34E+00	1.13E+00	1.02E+00	2.56E-01	1.00E+01	1.12E+00	4.29E+00	3.75E+00	3.57E+00	2.19E-01	1.18E+00
ETfw	CTUe	2.30E+01	6.79E+00	1.37E+01	4.75E+00	6.62E+00	8.68E-01	1.86E+00	6.72E-01	3.61E+02	1.49E+01	7.29E+00	7.69E+00	3.33E+01	2.04E+00	6.43E+00
ERnr	MJ, net calorific value	1.46E+01	2.36E+01	6.08E+01	1.68E+01	2.30E+01	1.62E+01	6.89E+00	2.43E+00	9.73E+01	1.38E+01	2.87E+01	3.33E+01	8.78E+01	5.39E+00	3.55E+01
Eutrfw	kg P-Eq	1.19E-04	1.29E-04	3.82E-04	9.15E-05	1.26E-04	1.16E-05	3.33E-05	1.17E-05	5.26E-03	1.13E-04	6.09E-04	6.80E-04	6.24E-04	3.83E-05	1.73E-04
Eutrm	kg N-Eq	7.18E-04	1.17E-03	3.19E-03	1.21E-03	1.71E-03	2.75E-04	8.49E-04	8.64E-05	8.80E-02	1.69E-03	2.75E-03	2.90E-03	6.72E-03	4.13E-04	1.56E-03
Eutrt	mol N-Eq	9.47E-03	1.30E-02	3.48E-02	1.34E-02	1.88E-02	2.92E-03	9.27E-03	9.34E-04	6.69E-01	1.74E-02	2.81E-02	3.00E-02	4.51E-02	2.77E-03	1.27E-02
HTc	CTUh	3.62E-09	4.85E-09	9.63E-09	3.50E-09	4.94E-09	1.35E-09	3.27E-09	1.23E-09	7.06E-08	6.82E-09	7.53E-09	8.60E-09	1.68E-08	1.03E-09	4.28E-09
HTnc	CTUh	7.83E-09	1.20E-08	3.48E-08	8.94E-09	1.23E-08	1.05E-09	5.04E-09	1.59E-09	5.25E-07	1.02E-08	1.73E-08	1.79E-08	2.65E-08	1.63E-09	8.11E-09
Irhh	kBq U235-Eq	3.17E-02	3.99E-02	1.02E+00	3.12E-02	4.13E-02	1.93E-03	1.03E-02	3.30E-03	3.13E-01	2.28E-02	4.86E-01	6.07E-01	1.96E+00	1.20E-01	1.12E+00
LU	dimensionless	4.18E+00	5.63E+00	1.50E+01	4.90E+00	6.98E+00	1.66E-01	5.15E+00	1.47E+00	5.34E+02	1.13E+02	9.97E+02	1.06E+03	1.23E+01	7.57E-01	4.87E+00
Teae	kg Sb-Eq	8.54E-06	1.34E-05	3.71E-05	9.23E-06	1.24E-05	1.99E-07	1.53E-06	5.76E-07	9.84E-05	4.10E-06	4.50E-06	4.98E-06	2.11E-05	1.30E-06	5.15E-06
OD	kg CFC-11-Eq	2.53E-08	2.79E-08	5.63E-08	2.00E-08	2.73E-08	3.24E-08	1.06E-08	3.58E-09	3.87E-07	1.93E-08	2.39E-08	2.82E-08	6.66E-08	4.09E-09	2.18E-08
Pmf	disease incidence	4.96E-08	5.39E-08	1.14E-07	4.73E-08	6.75E-08	4.05E-09	4.95E-08	1.32E-08	1.28E-06	8.45E-08	1.10E-07	1.18E-07	1.71E-07	1.05E-08	3.59E-08
POFhh	kg NMVOC-Eq	3.19E-03	6.93E-03	1.49E-02	5.95E-03	8.23E-03	1.85E-03	3.42E-03	6.13E-04	5.06E-02	4.24E-03	2.26E-02	1.99E-02	1.23E-02	7.55E-04	4.01E-03
WU	m ³ world Eq deprived	1.23E+00	1.07E-01	6.84E-01	7.82E-02	1.07E-01	2.14E-02	3.45E-02	1.19E-02	7.63E+01	3.05E-01	2.70E+00	2.49E+00	2.15E+00	1.32E-01	6.71E-01

Table A14. Impact contribution results of the LCA for the 15 products (Functional Unit: 1 kg of P₂O₅).

Impact category	Unit	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15
AC	mol H ⁺ -Eq	1.24E-02	3.20E-03	5.51E-03	1.79E-03	2.38E-03	1.40E-03	5.65E-03	1.01E-03	1.56E-01	No P ₂ O ₅	4.53E-02	4.43E-02	4.33E-01	No P ₂ O ₅	2.21E-02
CC	kg CO ₂ -Eq	3.30E+00	2.70E+00	3.02E+00	1.25E+00	1.62E+00	1.40E+00	2.27E+00	6.16E-01	9.51E+00	No P ₂ O ₅	2.08E+01	1.68E+01	6.82E+01	No P ₂ O ₅	4.96E+00
ETfw	CTUe	8.59E+01	3.95E+00	5.47E+00	1.84E+00	2.48E+00	1.07E+00	4.12E+00	1.61E+00	3.43E+02	No P ₂ O ₅	3.54E+01	3.44E+01	6.36E+02	No P ₂ O ₅	2.70E+01
ERnr	MJ, net calorific value	5.45E+01	1.37E+01	2.43E+01	6.52E+00	8.59E+00	2.01E+01	1.53E+01	5.83E+00	9.23E+01	No P ₂ O ₅	1.39E+02	1.49E+02	1.68E+03	No P ₂ O ₅	1.49E+02
Eutrfw	kg P-Eq	4.46E-04	7.53E-05	1.53E-04	3.55E-05	4.72E-05	1.44E-05	7.38E-05	2.81E-05	4.99E-03	No P ₂ O ₅	2.95E-03	3.04E-03	1.19E-02	No P ₂ O ₅	7.26E-04
Eutrm	kg N-Eq	2.68E-03	6.81E-04	1.28E-03	4.71E-04	6.38E-04	3.41E-04	1.88E-03	2.07E-04	8.35E-02	No P ₂ O ₅	1.34E-02	1.30E-02	1.29E-01	No P ₂ O ₅	6.58E-03
Eutrt	mol N-Eq	3.54E-02	7.54E-03	1.39E-02	5.19E-03	7.03E-03	3.61E-03	2.05E-02	2.24E-03	6.35E-01	No P ₂ O ₅	1.36E-01	1.34E-01	8.62E-01	No P ₂ O ₅	5.33E-02
HTc	CTUh	1.35E-08	2.82E-09	3.85E-09	1.36E-09	1.85E-09	1.67E-09	7.24E-09	2.94E-09	6.70E-08	No P ₂ O ₅	3.65E-08	3.84E-08	3.22E-07	No P ₂ O ₅	1.80E-08
HTnc	CTUh	2.92E-08	7.01E-09	1.39E-08	3.47E-09	4.62E-09	1.30E-09	1.12E-08	3.81E-09	4.98E-07	No P ₂ O ₅	8.42E-08	8.02E-08	5.07E-07	No P ₂ O ₅	3.41E-08
Irhh	kBq U235-Eq	1.19E-01	2.32E-02	4.07E-01	1.21E-02	1.55E-02	2.39E-03	2.27E-02	7.93E-03	2.97E-01	No P ₂ O ₅	2.36E+00	2.71E+00	3.75E+01	No P ₂ O ₅	4.72E+00
LU	dimensionless	1.56E+01	3.28E+00	5.99E+00	1.90E+00	2.61E+00	2.05E-01	1.14E+01	3.52E+00	5.07E+02	No P ₂ O ₅	4.84E+03	4.75E+03	2.36E+02	No P ₂ O ₅	2.05E+01
Teae	kg Sb-Eq	3.19E-05	7.81E-06	1.48E-05	3.58E-06	4.66E-06	2.46E-07	3.40E-06	1.38E-06	9.33E-05	No P ₂ O ₅	2.18E-05	2.22E-05	4.04E-04	No P ₂ O ₅	2.16E-05
OD	kg CFC-11-Eq	9.44E-08	1.62E-08	2.25E-08	7.75E-09	1.02E-08	4.01E-08	2.35E-08	8.58E-09	3.67E-07	No P ₂ O ₅	1.16E-07	1.26E-07	1.27E-06	No P ₂ O ₅	9.16E-08
Pmf	disease incidence	1.85E-07	3.14E-08	4.54E-08	1.84E-08	2.52E-08	5.01E-09	1.10E-07	3.16E-08	1.22E-06	No P ₂ O ₅	5.35E-07	5.28E-07	3.27E-06	No P ₂ O ₅	1.51E-07
POFhh	kg NMVOC-Eq	1.19E-02	4.03E-03	5.95E-03	2.31E-03	3.08E-03	2.29E-03	7.59E-03	1.47E-03	4.80E-02	No P ₂ O ₅	1.09E-01	8.89E-02	2.35E-01	No P ₂ O ₅	1.68E-02
WU	m ³ world Eq deprived	4.58E+00	6.24E-02	2.74E-01	3.03E-02	4.01E-02	2.64E-02	7.64E-02	2.85E-02	7.24E+01	No P ₂ O ₅	1.31E+01	1.11E+01	4.12E+01	No P ₂ O ₅	2.82E+00

Table A15. Impact contribution results of the LCA for the 15 products (Functional Unit: 1 kg of 1 kg of K₂O)

Impact category	Unit	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15
AC	mol H ⁺ -Eq	2.35E-03	3.65E-02	4.19E-02	2.04E-03	7.04E-03	2.22E-03	5.09E-02	1.15E-02	4.54E-02	1.86E-03	3.91E-02	3.36E-02	2.33E-02	No K ₂ O	2.93E-02
CC	kg CO ₂ -Eq	6.27E-01	3.08E+01	2.30E+01	1.43E+00	4.80E+00	2.21E+00	2.04E+01	7.03E+00	2.77E+00	3.94E-01	1.80E+01	1.27E+01	3.67E+00	No K ₂ O	6.56E+00
ETfw	CTUe	1.63E+01	4.51E+01	4.16E+01	2.10E+00	7.33E+00	1.70E+00	3.72E+01	1.84E+01	1.00E+02	5.22E+00	3.06E+01	2.60E+01	3.43E+01	No K ₂ O	3.57E+01
ERnr	MJ, net calorific value	1.04E+01	1.57E+02	1.85E+02	7.44E+00	2.54E+01	3.19E+01	1.38E+02	6.66E+01	2.69E+01	4.85E+00	1.20E+02	1.13E+02	9.04E+01	No K ₂ O	1.97E+02
Eutrfw	kg P-Eq	8.48E-05	8.60E-04	1.16E-03	4.05E-05	1.40E-04	2.28E-05	6.66E-04	3.21E-04	1.46E-03	3.99E-05	2.55E-03	2.30E-03	6.42E-04	No K ₂ O	9.60E-04
Eutrm	kg N-Eq	5.10E-04	7.77E-03	9.72E-03	5.38E-04	1.89E-03	5.40E-04	1.70E-02	2.37E-03	2.43E-02	5.94E-04	1.15E-02	9.82E-03	6.92E-03	No K ₂ O	8.70E-03
Eutrt	mol N-Eq	6.73E-03	8.60E-02	1.06E-01	5.93E-03	2.08E-02	5.72E-03	1.85E-01	2.56E-02	1.85E-01	6.11E-03	1.18E-01	1.02E-01	4.64E-02	No K ₂ O	7.05E-02
HTc	CTUh	2.57E-09	3.22E-08	2.93E-08	1.55E-09	5.47E-09	2.65E-09	6.53E-08	3.36E-08	1.95E-08	2.39E-09	3.15E-08	2.91E-08	1.73E-08	No K ₂ O	2.38E-08
HTnc	CTUh	5.56E-09	8.00E-08	1.06E-07	3.96E-09	1.37E-08	2.05E-09	1.01E-07	4.35E-08	1.45E-07	3.57E-09	7.26E-08	6.07E-08	2.73E-08	No K ₂ O	4.51E-08
Irhh	kBq U235-Eq	2.25E-02	2.65E-01	3.09E+00	1.38E-02	4.58E-02	3.78E-03	2.05E-01	9.05E-02	8.66E-02	8.01E-03	2.03E+00	2.05E+00	2.02E+00	No K ₂ O	6.24E+00
LU	dimensionless	2.97E+00	3.74E+01	4.56E+01	2.17E+00	7.72E+00	3.25E-01	1.03E+02	4.02E+01	1.48E+02	3.96E+01	4.18E+03	3.60E+03	1.27E+01	No K ₂ O	2.71E+01
Teae	kg Sb-Eq	6.07E-06	8.92E-05	1.13E-04	4.09E-06	1.38E-05	3.90E-07	3.07E-05	1.58E-05	2.72E-05	1.44E-06	1.88E-05	1.68E-05	2.18E-05	No K ₂ O	2.86E-05
OD	kg CFC-11-Eq	1.80E-08	1.85E-07	1.71E-07	8.84E-09	3.02E-08	6.35E-08	2.12E-07	9.80E-08	1.07E-07	6.78E-09	1.00E-07	9.54E-08	6.86E-08	No K ₂ O	1.21E-07
Pmf	disease incidence	3.52E-08	3.58E-07	3.46E-07	2.10E-08	7.47E-08	7.95E-09	9.90E-07	3.61E-07	3.55E-07	2.97E-08	4.61E-07	4.00E-07	1.76E-07	No K ₂ O	2.00E-07
POFhh	kg NMVOC-Eq	2.27E-03	4.60E-02	4.52E-02	2.63E-03	9.11E-03	3.64E-03	6.84E-02	1.68E-02	1.40E-02	1.49E-03	9.45E-02	6.73E-02	1.27E-02	No K ₂ O	2.23E-02
WU	m ³ world Eq deprived	8.71E-01	7.13E-01	2.08E+00	3.46E-02	1.19E-01	4.19E-02	6.89E-01	3.25E-01	2.11E+01	1.07E-01	1.13E+01	8.42E+00	2.22E+00	No K ₂ O	3.73E+00

Annex III. Complementary Results from the Assessment of the Use on Field of the alternative fertilising products

Table 25 Estimated Price according Farming Type and Production Costs

